

Meaning Making and Variation in Depression: Depressive Suicidal Thoughts as Meaningful

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Introduction

Within the last decades phenomenological research in psychopathologies has been flourishing, allowing new perspectives that further our understanding of the complex and to some degree still uncharted field (Kendler 2008). The reason for the newly blooming field is that there are still too many problems within psychiatry: The increasingly growing cases of mental disorders every year, a diagnosis system that is not able to keep up neither theoretically nor practically, with new explanations for stress and depression being brought to light every other year, and an increasing number of overdiagnoses (Brodersen 2017). Even with enormous efforts within the landscape of psychiatry that diligently seeks to improve our understanding of psychiatric disorders by either adopting a categorical or dimensional view, there still is a “[...] lack of improvement [that] motivates a refocusing of existing psychiatric research agendas” (Stephan et al. 2016, p. 77). These recent developments certainly seem to call for a reformation within the field of psychopathology, especially when considering that there seems to be an adherence to a rather biological, reductionistic approach that does not consider the subjective, and “any serious study of the mind, or ‘psyche’ must involve the considerations of consciousness, subjectivity, or the first-person point of view” (Parnas, Sass, and Zahavi 2012, p. 274).

Most of the modern knowledge concerning mental disorders stems from young diagnosis manuals, that only came into existence, as we know them today, within the last 70 years, containing some of the first glossary of descriptions of the diagnostic categories that focused on clinical use.¹ The diagnostic criteria are based on a value-free science, a technologization, that “Whilst not the aim of that trend, it often dehumanized relationships.” (Pereira, Gonçalves, and Bizzari 2018), where a ‘doing-to’ rather than a ‘being-with’ was prioritized suggesting an overarching tendency, where the focus was that of an objective science, that still tries to categorize and systematize psychiatric disorders based on positivism and empiricism (Pereira, Gonçalves, and Bizzari 2018). Depression, for example, has for a long period of time *not* been recognized as a disorder, which seems to be in direct correlation to the lack of experience hereof, as well as other psychopathologies. A sign of this is the expansive growth in the numbers of depression diagnoses, which, according to WHO has risen by 18% in just a decade from 2005-15, and by 2020 there is an estimated number of 264

¹ <https://www.psychiatry.org/psychiatrists/practice/dsm/history-of-the-dsm>

million cases.² This extreme growth of diagnoses implies a fundamental problem regarding depression, which calls for attention.

The naturalistic sciences in charge of diagnosing are founded upon an operationalism which operates/uses the diagnosis manuals such as the ICD-11 (International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems) and the DSM-V (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders), respectively the European and American diagnosis manuals. These manuals try to clarify whether a person is experiencing a mental or behavioural disorder, in order to reduce the burden and stress that the patients undergo and provide adequate treatment. So, then what is wrong? Operationalism constitutes the notion that the definitions of the terms within the practice are operational. And operational terms are defined by the definitions of the operation – this means that depression is defined by the test of depression (Marková and Berrios 2016) thus leaving out the subjective and intersubjective, and taking a narrow stance that leaves out much of what mental disorders are *actually* about, primarily the subject herself (Bizzari 2019).

This paper will argue that a phenomenological approach towards depression will allow us to perceive the volatile disorder in new light, allowing a more nuanced and complex understanding of the phenomenon to emerge, potentially leading to a reassessment of the current practice. In order to do so, I will first have to clarify the problems faced in operationalism, and how a person-centred approach paves the way for said practice, since issues between a phenomenological field and psychiatry still persists. I will try to bridge the gap by offering an enactive approach that seeks to unify the incompatibilities between an objective and subjective approach. This paper will then offer two distinct accounts: one of sense-making and meaning and one of a phenomenological analysis of the lived experience in depression. The first is useful to clarify how an autonomous subject makes sense of the world surrounding us, how we form opinions, what we consider valuable, and the second aims at giving a more descriptive understanding of the case at hand. Finally, I will use phenomenological qualitative interviews as tools to gain a deeper insight into the phenomenon of depression and nuance some of the core aspects pertaining to the disorder, showing that there is great variation in the lived experiences of person's with depression, which has yet to be explored, and I will describe what happens during suicidal ideation and the depressive suicide, and how the person with depression in the moments leading up to the depressive suicide, as well as their final moments, finds meaning and solace.

² World Health Organization, 2020.

I. Phenomenological Psychopathology: Towards a Person-Centred Approach in The Study of Psychiatric Disorders

Phenomenology shows us a way around some of the problems mentioned in the introduction, but to be able to show what such an approach has to offer, a further undertaking of what the issue at hand entails is required. Therefore, this chapter will take start off with a description of mentioned operationalism regarding its inadequacies when concerned with psychopathology, before embarking on the *what* and *how* of phenomenological psychopathology – and why this approach is advantageous if we wish to understand first-person perspective: it will further the understanding of mental disorders as a whole, innovate the research, and thereby be able to give better treatment as a result thereof, making such an perspective beneficial for both patient and practitioner. But in order for phenomenology to have an impact on the psychiatric field, as it is a tremendously tangled and compound field, an integrative model, the enactive model, will be shown to offer a bridge that takes into account the myriad of factors that might be the cause behind a psychological disorder.

I, 1. Operationalism

When the doubt exists of whether a person is experiencing depression or not, a professional, usually a Doctor of Medicine, will conduct a structured interview based upon the diagnostic manuals. The interview will consist of a string of questions based upon the listed criteria for said diagnosis – and according to ICD-11 depression is characterized by “lowering of mood, reduction of energy, and decrease in activity. Capacity for enjoyment, interest, and concentration is reduced, and marked tiredness after even minimum effort is common”³. Depression is defined in the ICD-11 as being an affective-disorder, which is described as disruptions and changes founded in mood.

This form of methodology is the operationalism described earlier. The need for operationalism occurred as a way for securing reliability within psychiatry, as a compliance between diagnosis given to the same patient by different professionals. Operationalism replaced the prior way of diagnosing, which had its foundation in comparing descriptions and psychoanalysis. It is based upon a specific reductionism, namely the principle that if a subject field can be reduced to a simpler subject field, then a scientific examination (for instance, one

³ <https://icd.who.int/browse11/l-m/en#/http://id.who.int/icd/entity/1194756772> 6A-70

among those I mentioned) of the latter can be used to explain the former.⁴ Therefore, within operationalism we can find the assumption that deviating psychological symptoms are phenomena that can be explained by biology, and operationalism can likewise be viewed as a wish for an objective psychiatry. This longing within psychiatry for objectivity has resulted in a methodology that is based upon the same epistemological criteria, that are also applied within the somatic medical science. But a problem arises, as the same criteria are not that easily transferred, since symptoms and indications are not necessarily the same within somatic and psychiatric fields. In the somatic medical science, symptoms are nothing more than accessory landmarks towards the actual dysfunction, e.g. that yellow skin is an indication that points towards hepatitis-C. On the other hand, in psychiatry, the “symptoms and signs constitute both the diagnostic tools as well as the diagnostic products” (Marková and Berrios 2016, p. 191), which means that “psychological disorders are defined via the patients suffering phenomena – disturbances, that encapsules the patients experiences of herself, the surrounding world, and other people” (Zahavi and Parnas 2009, p. 85)⁵. In other words: psychological disorders *are* the distressing symptoms.

Since these symptoms, as quoted in the ICD-11, refer to the patient’s experience, they are not reducible as being rooted in matter in the same way that somatic dysfunctions are, and they will therefore not be able to share the same epistemological basis (Marková and Berrios 2016). A consequence of the fact that symptoms within psychiatry are understood in the same way as those in the somatic illnesses, is that outer indications within psychological disorders are viewed as symptoms, which are actually the essential nature of the disorders. This has led to a decontextualization of the definitions in psychiatry, which are incompatible with a clear understanding of the disorders (Parnas and Sass 2008).

The inadequacy of this description method calls for a further expansion, that can accommodate a more nuanced understanding of subjective experiences (Ratcliffe 2015), and further a more person-centred method that includes the actual lived experience of the patients. This is where a phenomenological approach will be of use, and theories developed within this method will be touched upon in the next section.

⁴ E.g. in the explanation of bodily functions with the help of molecular biology, which in turn is explained by atoms and so forth. (Zahavi and Parnas 2009)

⁵ Own translation.

I, 2. A Phenomenological Approach

That phenomenology places itself up against the two-world doctrine, which dictates a dualistic view of there being the world, as it is for us, and the world, as it is in itself (Zahavi 2003), shouldn't come as a surprise, neither should the view that phenomenology has something to offer within the realm of psychology and psychiatry. This has been clear ever since the emergence of Edmund Husserl's (1859-1938) phenomenology and the likes such as Jaspers (1883-1969), Katz (1884-1953), Heidegger (1889-1976), Merleau-Ponty (1908-1961), Sartre (1905-1980), Straus (1891-1975), Binswanger (1881-1966), Minkowski (1885-1972), and many more, all of whom explicitly commented on the practice of psychology of their time. Though there exists reason to differentiate between phenomenological psychology, phenomenological philosophy, and even phenomenological psychiatry, trying to clarify the differences between the branches and their fields of attention, could easily require an entire academic paper: For our purposes, a quick differentiation should be satisfactory, as to not mix up the different fields that each of these branches evolves around.

In the later works of Husserl, he distinguishes between a transcendental phenomenology on the one hand, and a phenomenological psychology on the other (Husserl 1977). Both of which settle themselves within consciousness, but with two different scopes. The phenomenological psychology intends to clarify and examine the intentional consciousness in a non-reductive way, which enables it to be a psychology that takes up a first-person perspective and allures the severity of exactly this, as to not diminish the lived experience of the subject herself (Zahavi 2018); Unlike the transcendental philosophy, which Husserl saw as a philosophy, as it stays in the pre-philosophical natural attitude, and does not try to create a new foundation. Husserl's main concern certainly was the transcendental philosophy, but he was aware that his works did not only conform hereto, and that his analyses could also be of great relevance within psychology. Because if psychology is to evolve itself, it needs to take into consideration the lived experience of the subjects, and this is exactly what phenomenology has been shown to offer. And for psychology to do so it must suspend the theoretical prejudices, that it has naively overtaken from other scientific disciplines. In doing so, Husserl was convinced that psychology would eventually lead to a transcendental phenomenological philosophy, by bracketing given knowledge, and laying out a new foundation without prejudice (Husserl 1970). Husserl's theories created a notion within psychology, one example is David Katz and his contribution to the field with his phenomenology of touch and colours, which itself was soon to create ripples within the field:

“[...] he [Katz] insisted that the psychologist should begin by deliberately "bracketing" his physical, physiological, and philosophical biases and attempt to observe phenomena as they are actually presented. The phenomenal world thus viewed contains properties and relationships that escape the notice of the physically or physiologically oriented observer.” (MacLeod 1954, p. 3)

The link between phenomenology and psychology is recent, but nonetheless an important one. It has grown into psychiatry as well, and many have argued for the necessity of phenomenology in fields such as pedagogy and nurse studies (Zahavi and Martiny 2019). And Jaspers even argued that “the psychiatrist’s competence is really commensurate with how far his education and knowledge would qualify him to belong to the philosophic faculty.” (Jaspers 1963, p. 36).

The reason for this is constituted in the view that the lived experience of the subject is able to explain to us what is *actually* happening when a patient suffers from a mental disorder, since the phenomenological approach seeks a “philosophical analysis of the objects different appearances and in connection to a reflexive examination of the structures of comprehension, that allows the objects to show themselves, as they are.” (Zahavi, 2003, p. 13)⁶. To be able to understand the objects, we do not have to remove the subjective perspective, which has been put in a bad light due to an ever more growing objectification within sciences, but on the other hand to examine the correlation between these. In this way phenomenology challenges the dichotomy of subject and object, which indicates that the world is as it is, independently of our understanding of it. Within phenomenology subjectivity and first-person perspective are essential if we want to clarify the phenomena that inhabit our lived experience. Ratcliffe (2015) argues that this calls for a shift within psychiatry from the unpersonal to the personal, as this shift is still aligned with the phenomenological method.

The phenomenological method, which has its starting point in Husserl’s epoché (Husserl 1970; 2014), ascribes a suspension or bracketing of our most fundamental approaches to the world – our natural attitude. The suspension of said attitude is the starting point for a clarification of many pre-suppositions that we usually adhere to our experiences, as a form of background for our view of the world, that through time have grown into habits, that are so ingrained in us, that one does not realize this, and it seems to some extent impossible to get rid of (Ratcliffe 2015). And it is exactly these ground structures for our consciousness and

⁶ Own translation

experiences that phenomenology primarily focuses on, and which is easily viewed in phenomenological qualitative interviews. The phenomenological interview forms a method that tries to collect a detailed account of descriptive experiences from the interviewee as possible. The phenomenological qualitative interview is also, according to Hammersley & Atkinson (2007), an interview that breaks down the barrier between interviewer and interviewee, allowing not only an interview, but also a conversation between two equally engaged agents, giving room for a first-person perspective to emerge, where the interviewer guides the interviewee, and letting the two subjects interact with each other as people. Thus, generating new knowledge and letting go of the fundamental presuppositions.

“It is a distinctive feature of social research that the ‘objects’ studied are in fact ‘subjects’, in the sense that they have consciousness and agency. Moreover, unlike physical objects or animals, they produce accounts of themselves and their works.” (Hammersley and Atkinson 2007, p. 97)

The interview is founded on letting the interviewee continue to speak for as long as she is talking about her experience and not interrupt her (Giorgi 2009), and letting the interviewer take a second-person perspective, engaging empathically and letting reciprocity be the main goal of the interviewer (Zahavi 2015). This will lead to a more open interview, “in which you are not out to confirm already held theories [...] [Whilst] You do not come to the interview as neutral” (Høffding and Martiny 2016, p. 4). The interviewer comes to the interview as a subject without strong beliefs or a hypothesis that is to be proven, letting both participants participate in a knowledge generation process, trying to steer free of what Husserl might have called a biased objective knowledge.

A second benefit of the phenomenological qualitative interview, and thereby also the phenomenological approach, is that usually when talking about experiences, let us say depression, the interviewee will often fall back upon using professional language, that she has picked up unconsciously either when reading about it online, overhearing people talk about it, or even using the words that the interviewer puts in her mouth. For instance, in the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D or HDRS), the first questions revolve around whether the patient have had a depressive mood, or later if there is an experience of retardation. The patient will find herself in a position to use the language from the questions to answer them, and automatically continue to use these words to describe their position – but what does these words entail? That is what the phenomenological interview tries to clarify, letting the patient

speak for themselves, and when starting to theorize an experience, the interviewer should gently guide her back to the descriptions (Giorgi 2009).⁷ Then she should continue to guide the interviewee further and further into these experiences, the interviewer lets her evolve on her own thoughts and subtly hint to try and let the patient gain further insights into her own experiences, but also to increase the interviewers understanding of the lived experience of depression, to understand at a more theoretically level the subjective and intersubjective relations towards themselves, the world, and others (Zahavi 2018). Thereby, the phenomenological approach does not only try to clarify the contents of experiences, but also the structures of these. A phenomenological approach of a psychopathological experience does not concern only *what* presents itself to the patient, but also a *how*. E.g. one would not only be interested in the feeling of guilt, but also in the fundamental structure of feeling something at all, going deeper into what guilt could be for that specific patient. Therefore, the perspective of phenomenology upon psychopathology will aim our scope on the disturbances of the fundamental structures of experience, and as Ratcliffe describes in his phenomenological method of examining depression: “reflection upon disturbances of world-experience” (Ratcliffe 2015), where world-experience is to be understood as Husserl’s life world.

To summarize, the phenomenological approach allows for a first-person perspective to emerge, where one tries to break from the natural attitude, which is to be understood as “[...] the attitude of everyday life [...] where most things are simply taken for granted.”(Giorgi 2009, p. 87). Where one can view the ‘objects’ of, in this particular case, psychiatric disorders, free from the natural attitude, in an unburdened view, that suspends “any assumptions about causal explanations of a disorder, [...] and instead try to grasp the patient’s experience as best as possible” (Fuchs 2014, p. 404). This approach can be useful to the understanding of psychopathology as the undertakings of the lived experience of a patient suffering from a mental disorder, proves not only of value to the patient herself, but also to the practitioner. In fact, the approach gains further insights into how the mental disorder is *actually* experienced, and tries to make it more subjective, since it recognizes that the mental disorders *are* linked to the subject. Even though the research and attention regarding the more personal, such as interpersonal emotions, have been somewhat less explored (Henriksen and Skodlar, n.d.).

⁷ E.g. the experience of laying in the bed for hours on end without getting up instead of stopping there, and take it as a fundamental experience of depression, try to dwell further into this, by asking questions such as: “how did you perceive time?”, “what did you think about?” etc.

I, 3. Enactivism

As mentioned earlier, a phenomenological inspired enactive perspective offers the idea that psychiatric disorders are disordered patterns of sense-making (de Haan 2020). Sense-making and what it entails will be briefly touched upon in this chapter, and a more detailed explanation of sense-making will follow in chapter II. This chapter will focus on the *what* and *why* of the enactive approach, as to lay out a foundation for the rest of the thesis.

The enactive approach took its starting point in the book *Embodied Mind* (Varela, Thompson, and Rosch 1991) which attempted to reconcile the cognitive sciences with phenomenology, and challenge the more classical views on cognition, which sought to understand common-sense and how we interact with the world as a sort of programmed computer. But “[...] even the simplest cognitive action requires a seemingly infinite amount of knowledge, which we take for granted.” (Varela, Thompson, and Rosch 1991, p. 148). Therefore, they sought to understand the way in which we are in the world without predefined boundaries, not by trying to uncover more and more sophisticated rules to ‘code into the computer’ – as this would continue infinitum – but rather to understand our common-sense as “the very essence of *creative cognition*” (Varela, Thompson, and Rosch 1991, p. 148). By trying to understand our cognition as, and through, common-sense enabled the enactive perspective, which is further enabled by drawing on notions presented by Heidegger, Gadamer, and the phenomena of interpretation “[...] understood as the *enactment* or *bringing forth* of meaning from a background of understanding.” (Varela, Thompson, and Rosch 1991, p. 149). Through our common-sense we navigate the world with this know-how, and with this interpretation of meaning in the world, we are able to do through our being-in-the-world that will never be separable from “[...] our bodies, our language, and our social history – in short, from our embodiment” (Varela, Thompson, and Rosch 1991, p. 149). So the enactive approach is an understanding of how we navigate the world as complex beings that do not just neutrally go through the world, but rather are constantly receiving information from our environment, social sphere, culture, and language through our bodies, because fundamentally we “enact a world” (Varela, Thompson, and Rosch 1991), meaning that the felt world is enacted or constituted by this continuously engaging and making sense of the world. The theory then becomes an understanding of how we make sense of the world as living bodies,⁸ understanding it with all its different facets that is pertaining hereto.

⁸ As mentioned, what sense-making actually entails will be unfolded upon in chapter III, for now this explanation will suffice for the understanding of the enactive approach.

Earlier we have seen the need for a new model in psychiatry, that takes into account the person-centred experiences, and try to divert itself from the operationalism, that seems to be the root of the fundamental problems faced in, especially, psychiatry. De Haan problematizes these exact core issues and tries to solve the problem of how naturalistic tendencies have been increasingly overtaking the modus within mental disorders. In her view there seems to be an integration problem that has its foundations in the dualistic gap of psychological and physiological, of the inner and outer realm. Therefore, she proposes adopting an enactive view that constitutes a holistic picture that engages mind, body, and world in one instead of the two-place relation.

Within psychiatry, and the mental disorders it tries to examine, there exist the model of biopsychosocial approach, which generalizes three main dimensions: 1) the experiential, 2) physiological, and 3) sociocultural. In order to understand the enactive approach, it is important to touch upon these three main dimensions, and in addition to these three dimensions, de Haan is arguing for an additional fourth dimension: 4) the existential dimension, which, unsurprisingly, plays an important role in the enactive approach.

The experiential dimension refers directly to the patients' experiences, meaning that this dimension takes into account the experiences of the patient as they live through them. Since a major turning point of phenomenology, and this thesis in particular, aims at first-person lived experiences in order to clarify the specific disorders, the cruciality of this dimension should be justified.

The physiological dimension concerns the "genetic, anatomical, biochemical, and neurological aspects of psychiatric disorders" (de Haan 2020, p. 10), and generally include all of those bodily processes and autonomous bodily functions which are necessary to include if we are to gain the holistic picture that de Haan is arguing for, since we are our bodies, and it is through our bodies that we interact with the world.

The sociocultural dimension is a bit more complex; it touches upon the understanding that human beings are already beforehand interconnected with each other, our environment. We are already always interconnected with each other and our environment, bound up and affected by norms, habits, tendencies, why we react as we react, or the actions that we take. We are all parts of different social and cultural groups, stretching from communities with family, friends, and work, to being a citizen in a certain country, including even material, economic, or political aspects that in a certain way affects a patient's life-world. All of these

shapes us in some way, and/ or if one were to exclude these different spheres, then we wouldn't fully be able to understand the guilt or shame that comes in different varieties when considering psychopathologies, as norms and perception often play an important role in these.⁹ The point is that a mental disorder, can never be viewed in a vacuum, since we are always already engaged with the world, in whatever action, thought, perception, or feeling we are having or performing – even when we are by ourselves, e.g. the thought of an embarrassing statement said when a teenager, can keep us up at night even years later. And if there is to be an adequate understanding of mental disorders, then this dimension should with certainty be included.

The fourth dimension that de Haan is arguing for should be included is that of the existential dimension, which refers to the way in which people relate to and make sense of themselves and their situation. When arguing for an enactive psychiatry, especially the existential dimension calls for more attention, firstly since this has been left out in more structural foundation, and secondly since it is the newest and also the most controversial.¹⁰ The way we experience things, we do not just experience, “[...] but we can also *relate to* our experiences” (de Haan 2020, p. 12). By perceiving and experiencing we add another layer of judgement, where “I introduce [...] either sensory functions or cultural arrangements that are not actually my own.” (Merleau-Ponty 2014, p. 374). This relation to the world and the engagement with it, it does not become a neutral participation, since we are able to relate to how we engage with it and reflect upon our actions and how we are situated in certain social or cultural dynamics. This existential domain then offers an understanding of why we feel as we do, by being able to point out the cause and effect of internal feelings¹¹, thereby creating a reflexive relation, where values, meaning, and valences spring forth. Valences can best be understood in light of the affordance theory (Gibson 1979), where a more detailed description

⁹ E.g. if one were to try and imagine a person born on a deserted island, and consider said individual independent from the rest of the world, within their own lifeworld. By just starting this thought experiment one would miss the point, because it is impossible to imagine a person born on a deserted island, since if the person would be born there, the island would not be deserted – tying up a misconception of trying to perceive issues ostracized from the whole. A related example is that of ‘Robinson Crusoe’ given by Max Scheler, where Crusoe is marooned and completely alone on an island, where he, nonetheless, still feels the urge to imagine Otherness and relate to them. By the virtue of always already beforehand being part of a community, although an individual, where “the world of the Thou, or of the community, is [...] an *independent sphere of essential being*” (Scheler 2007, p. 236), that allows the conscious experience of that independent sphere to emerge and be present, just as much as, and as original, “as his individual ‘I-feeling’”(Scheler 1960, p. 373), making even the intersubjective feeling of being towards a community, even as imagined, a necessity, “he is *objectively* and originally oriented toward that community and realm.”(Scheler 1960, p. 374).

¹⁰ Although I would be surprised if anyone would consider 1-3 radical or controversial in any way.

¹¹ It is to be noted, that even though the existential domain offers a sort of causation explanation of our sense-making, it is also implicit, and we do not willingly choose the way in which we make sense of the world.

emerges. In the affordance theory valences are referred to as solicitations: where an affordance – which is the possibility of an action provided by the environment – stands out in a specific environment as being relevant to the individual, meaning that the individual solicits the field of affordances provided, which can be acted upon by the person. E.g. the action of drinking water from the tap, because the individual is thirsty (Bruineberg and Rietveld 2014). The affordances therefore have a certain *value*, that the individual can find either attractive or unattractive – de Haan therefore argues that in order to avoid confusion on whether something is better or worse, one is to refer to the solicitations as something purely basic or as having metabolic values, or just *valences*.

But valences and values are dynamic and can change over time, just as individuals grow older, the body changes, the environment changes and new *needs* arise in relation to oneself. And based on these, valences do not only *possess* an objective *value* directly attached to *themselves*, since individuals are much more complex and “we do not only want to stay alive, but also live a good life. [Where] our worlds are imbued with existential meaning.” (de Haan 2020, p. 168).¹² Our environment, in a healthy relation to the world, is full of meaning, and the environment itself is meaningful to the specific individual, since it also constitutes our survival. Meaning becomes existential when one considers the complexity of human beings, we are existential creatures that can reflect and relate to our own understanding and our social world – we want to live *good* lives, we want to be happy, be respected, and take a certain pride in ourselves. E.g. the act of maintaining a good relationship with our parents, friends, or co-workers can be meaningful if this gives the individual pleasure or is ascribed a certain *value*. It is to be noted, that even though valences, meaning, and values exist as reflective relation, they also inhabit a reflexive relation, since most of the time we are engaging with the world, we are not necessarily reflective. One may find themselves unable to remember whether they brushed their teeth this morning, or what they had for lunch yesterday. For example, a habit of avoiding social interactions because of panic attacks, may sooner rather than later, just be a force of unreflective habit and implicit without further thought, since the *value* of not getting hurt in a social context is guiding the individual as habitual knowledge. It is not a surprise that we do things all the time that are not inherently important to our survival, but rather to our wellbeing, and so values and valences do not refer to objective

¹² For now, the understanding of *meaning* within this domain is something that we rather quickly brush past, as the understanding of when something is meaningful to a specific individual and how a meaning-making takes place will become clearer in the following chapter, since the goal for now is to understand the enactive approach.

entities but are rather “[...] relative to the configuration of a specific person, with her specific history of interactions, her specific bodily experiences, her specific sociocultural upbringing and the specific sociocultural community of which she is part.” (de Haan 2020, p. 171). Taking into account all of the four dimensions that makes up a living person, it becomes clear that none of these can be understood in isolation from the other three, “experiences [1] depend on there being a bodily being [2] in an environment [3].” (de Haan 2020, p. 68), which can be viewed implicitly and explicitly 4).

The enactive approach, when observing psychopathologies, then becomes a framework, in which we are able to understand not only how the world is enacted by the cognitive agent and what goes amiss when, for example, one is suffering from depression. We are also able to see all the different dimensions that constitutes us as cognitive agents in a world that is not only restricted to an immediate nearness through our bodies, but also in a sociocultural dimension, where our experiences take place, in which we relate to. Furthermore, de Haan argues that valences, values, and meaning are not just mere extra adds to the way in how we perceive the world, but are so fundamentally ingrained in it that it is impossible to imagine a world without them. Therefore, we should make them part of a naturalistic world view, offering a bridge that lets a more *subjective* approach be reconciled with the more *objective* approach. The enactive framework thereby supports a new idea or framework that offers the complexity of human beings and all that entails on a most existential level, allowing the phenomenological method to gain wider acceptance within the studies of psychopathology.

II. Sense-Making and Meaning

Concerning meaning and sense-making, that was briefly mentioned in the previous chapter, a more nuanced and developed understanding of these are necessary if one wants to understand some of the problems faced in depression. De Haan defines sense-making as “the evaluative interaction of an organism with its environment” (de Haan 2020, p. 167), which can then be further divided or distinguished as three different categories of sense-making; (i) basic sense-making, (ii) existential sense-making or reflection, and (iii) ‘existentialised’ sense-making as the general sense-making of persons as transformed by (ii) (de Haan 2020); but before dwelling further on these, it is worthwhile to mention that other definitions of sense-making exists, as for example those of Thompson & Stapleton (2009) and Di Paolo & Thompson (2014) – which, compared to de Haan’s description of sense-making as an evaluative interaction with the environment, further takes into consideration notions such as intentionality and normativity. I would argue that de Haan’s definition, by not picking up such notions, adds not a vagueness, but rather a more embracing and nuanced understanding of what sense-making is. By not introducing agency and autonomy, her definition allows for a myriad of facets of what sense-making in cognitive, conscious beings entails. Since sense-making does not merely involve a reflective engagement with the world, where we always perceive and try to make sense of everything in our surroundings – which arguably would be considerably tiresome and overwhelming. Rather, it is something learned, it shapes and forms us, and allows us to reflexively make sense of the world in which we commute, taking into consideration the many inputs we receive in our everyday life, filtering out what requires our attention, and what does not; whilst at the same time allowing for normative and intentional aspects to emerge. Therefore, I seek to understand sense-making in the light of de Haan, as it just allows *that much more*. This in turn, if considering how the enactive approach rejects an inner-outer distinction, mind-world division, argues for a more intercorrelated understanding of world and being in perpetual dynamic relation, thereby aligning itself with the phenomenological approach by investigating the first-person lived experience, and in turn making it interdisciplinary.

Furthermore, the literature on meaning, meaning-making, sense-making, meaning in life, and so forth is stretched across a vast landscape of psy- and philosophy disciplines (including psychiatry, psychology, psychopathology, psychoanalysis, cognitive psychology, philosophy of mind etc.), and throughout the ages widely discussed in literature and religion, along many other studies that has been instigated towards a deeper understanding of meaning in life.

There exist here many subsections, such as, just to name a few, meaning frameworks and meaning-making (Park 2010), threat compensation (Proulx, Inzlicht, and Harmon-Jones 2012), meaning maintenance model (MMM; Heine, Proulx, and Vohs 2006), goals and goal pursuit (Carver and Scheier 1998), coping with trauma (Park 2010), identity (McAdams 2008), self-enhancement (Alicke and Sedikides 2009), and terror management theory (TMT; Greenberg, Pyszczynski, and Solomon 1986). Compared to these and the insurmountable literature concerned with the grand question of what it means to have meaning in one's life, Login S. George and Crystal L. Park (2016) argue that meaning, and more specifically meaning in life¹³, can be understood with added clarity, if one were to adopt a tripartite view of MIL, which takes into consideration the notions of *comprehension*, *purpose*, and *matter*. The idea of narrowing down what MIL entails to three concepts, comes from a desire to be more specific, since the concept of MIL would otherwise quickly become quite confusing – in the same manner, if one were to *not* distinguish between these three subsections, they would all rather quickly become a singular diffuse concept (George and Park 2016), seeing as they all interconnect and overlap to a certain extent. George and Park also argues that the diverse mentioned research and literature can be tied together in the common theme of sense-making (George and Park 2016), since MIL is concerned with how “people come to understand themselves, their environments, and their relationship to their environment.” (Markman, Proulx, and Lindberg 2013, p. 4), thereby creating a bridge between MIL, sense-making, and, for the purpose of this thesis, how meaning and a sense of meaning is so defining in psychopathology, furthering the research on this already interdisciplinary subject. Seeing that sense-making and stance-taking is so fundamental to our own understanding, and in virtue thereof MIL, it will be beneficial to give an adequate understanding hereof, before departing on the second part of this chapter, regarding MIL, *meaning*, meaning-making, and personal values, the purpose of which will be useful in the understanding of what happens in depression, and how the depressive suicide is a regaining of MIL, though extremely distorted.

II, 1. Sense-Making and Stance-Taking

To start off with the differences between the first two forms of sense-making, basic and explicit existential, is rather intuitive: basic sense-making is that which is inherent in all living beings, and revolves around the ability to distinguish “what is supportive of one's existence and what entails threats.” (de Haan 2020, p. 55); Whereas the existential sense-

¹³ From now on I will write the acronym ‘MIL’.

making is imbued with meaning, values, and meaningfulness, and, as de Haan points out, it is not that the fox grave isn't *meaningful* to the fox, it is *meaningful* to that particular fox, but it isn't experienced '*as being meaningful*' (de Haan 2020). To elaborate: basic sense-making is the way in which an organism makes sense of its environment and necessary needs to stay alive directly correlating hereto – such as eating, sleeping, find shelter etc. On the other hand, explicit existential sense-making is something unique to human beings that imbue the world with meaning, value, and valences, letting us engage with the environment in an existential manner, which turn diet, clothing, physical appearance etc. into ways of navigating the world. For example, the choosing of clothing isn't just a way to keep warm, but also a way to display status, as belonging to a certain group or class, a way to act professional, and to navigate the world based upon what we perceive around us. It is with explicit sense-making (ii) that we are able to make sense of things actively and reflectively, such as our stance relating to oneself and one's position, e.g. when considering one's feelings towards gender roles, one's dreams, aspirations, ideas, and what is regarded as '*good*' and '*bad*' for oneself and one's wellbeing. As Merleau-Ponty puts it: "only men see that they are nude. In the house that he builds for himself, man projects and realizes his preferred values." (Merleau-Ponty 1963, p. 174). This ties itself directly to the third form of sense-making (iii); the 'existentialised' sense-making as the general sense-making of persons as transformed by (ii). Since the need *or* urge to explicitly reflect upon e.g. gender issues, don't necessarily arise without a confrontation of specific perceived values, it is the person that is transformed by (ii), which then becomes *incorporated* unto our general reflexive sense-making. Existentialised sense-making is the way through which we navigate our *Umwelt* reflexively, which we are shown from an early age. One might consider it bad table manners to hold the fork in the right hand, but this is not something that is considered or springs forth without it coming into our thoughts. One might never have considered it, nor thought about it, since it was something shaped and formed in our upbringing, and thereby our environment, our social state, the capabilities of our bodies and so forth.¹⁴ The fact that our sense-making is socially and culturally dependent begs one to consider norms as well, making existentialised sense-making morally sensitive sense-making as such (de Haan 2020). By either adhering or deciding against norms of our environment one takes a stance, which always implies a certain

¹⁴ It is important to note, since it seems quite easy to ascribe a certain hierarchical scale to these sorts of sense-making, that the explicit existential sense-making is *not* an extra add-on to basic sense-making. Rather, they are *different*, and with reflection or explicit existential sense-making the whole person or system is transformed, creating the notion of (iii) 'existentialised' sense-making.

relation to these norms, that one cannot escape.¹⁵ And it is with the capacity for stance-taking that our worlds and sense-making is altogether different (de Haan 2020).

In consideration of stance-taking, the previous quote by Merleau-Ponty still seems applicable, since it not only shows the point of existential sense-making as both reflexive and reflective, but also how stance-taking is something that once learned can never be unlearned. Because much like a child previously running along playing nude in the city fountain suddenly becomes aware of nudity, she no longer wishes to show her body out of embarrassment by virtue of social stigma and so forth, and she can then never again unlearn, what has now been learned. Her personal identity has been transformed, and her sense-making has become existentialised; where her ability to sense-making is based upon the ability to stance-taking, of how we engage with the world based on norms fostered in our specific sociocultural groups, which are static in any way, but progresses throughout life. Meaning that these are reflexive, and reflective, understandings of how we engage with the world, which are unavoidable and often implicit – thereby, in light of an enactive approach, these are always co-constituted by our environment and an Other, making it an existential stance, that is no longer an organism-world (basic sense-making), but rather a person-world interaction, that changes how we perceive and take a stance on oneself, one's experiences, one's environment, and the consequences that follow:

“The meaningfulness of our worlds and the values that guide our actions, surpass the functional, the life-maintaining: with stance-taking a different kind of [...] ‘existential values’ [emerge], such as respect, honour, dignity, friendship, and love.” (de Haan 2020, p. 60)

Based upon the different dimensions, which were touched upon in the previous chapter, this does not entail that existentialised sense-making or sense-making is *just* an active participation, or choosing, of a particular subject throwing meaning unto the world, but rather it represents a dynamic symbiosis between individual and environment, since we are highly affected by sociocultural and existential dimensions.¹⁶ The pre-reflective way of being-in-the-world is shaped by those dimensions, and our unreflective and spontaneous sense-making is therefore also affected. It never is just a projection of meaning unto a neutral world¹⁷, nor is it

¹⁵ Take for example the prior example of Crusoe and the Other.

¹⁶ Thereby aligning existential and basic sense-making with the biopsychosocial approach intertwining them and allowing de Haan's fourth dimension to emerge more prominently

¹⁷ What one might call a subjectivist conception or interpretation.

a passive absorption of information, rather it is a ‘*relational function*’. Meaning that sense-making is bodily affective as well as an embodied activity, we affect the environment around us, as well as the environment affects us. We interact with our world, and the world interacts with us, and thus becomes a direct affective, interactive evaluation (de Haan 2020), where one is able to take a stance, affecting otherwise basic life maintaining functions. Borrowing a term from Thompson and Stapleton (2009), it becomes a “body-world dance”, in which we reflexively and explicitly consider the values and meaning that is encountered in our *Umwelt*.

Sense-making is then, in light of the enactive perspective, an understanding of a how an organism, or autonomous system makes sense of the world or environment, which, concerning conscious agents, becomes imbued with meaning, meaningfulness and so on that transform the entire system. This then begs the question of what makes something meaningful to a particular individual if we are not to fall into a category of just being products of our environment, as de Haan would suggest. It seems problematic if our selfhood or minimal self are nothing more than the outcome of complicated processes of social construct, being a mere matter of politics and culture, as proposed by Zahavi by taking into consideration the works by Husserl (1950; 1952; 1954; 1959; 1962; 1976; 2001), Heidegger (1988), Sartre (2003), and Merleau-Ponty (2012) – not to say that we aren’t constantly engaging in a dance with the world, which we shape and which shapes us. The point made by Zahavi is that there seems to be something inherently wrong with disregarding the notion of a minimal-self, since ‘I’ am first and foremost acquainted and familiar with myself. And if we were to have our pre-reflective ‘I’ derived from highly complex social structure, then there would only be experiences and perceptions, but no experiencer or perceiver (Zahavi 2019). However, this does not entail that our self is some sort of ontological independent soul substance that is distinct from and does not interact with the world, since that would let our body be a sort of holster, something in our possession, a tool that we can use to experience the world – rather “there is not ‘inner man,’ man is in and toward the world, and it is in the world that he knows himself. When I return to myself [...] I do not find a source of intrinsic truth, but rather a subject destined to the world.” (Merleau-Ponty 1963, p. 67). Through our perception a relationship is formed between consciousness and world, and neither can be reduced. Zahavi opts for a third middle position, where the minimal self “can be identified with the ubiquitous first-person character of the experiential phenomena. [And] if we want to ‘locate’ the experiential self, we shouldn’t look at *what* is experienced, but at *how* it is being experienced.” (Zahavi 2019, p. 302) – though this does not seem satisfactory, and if we want

to account for a deeper understanding of the minimal self, it seems that there is a need for incorporating historicity, sociality, and normativity since the minimal self, whilst being the experiencer, is likewise shaped, or adopts first-person values, or new meaning-making frameworks that are learned unto the dimension of experience, and incorporated into an unconscious navigation in a world full of meaning and value to that particular individual.

II, 2. Meaning in Life and the Tripartite View

In order to cut across the many different approaches to the grand question of meaning in life, Park and George not only argues for gathering the different subsections in the common theme of sense-making, but also argues for a tripartite view on meaning in life – which will allow a clearer outlook, that will not lump them together into a diffuse singular concept (George and Park 2016). As mentioned, the tripartite view takes into consideration *comprehension*, *purpose*, and *mattering*, and where the experience of meaning in one's life comes forth as making sense, with direction, and motivation by certain goals of value, and as in one's world (George and Park 2016; King et al. 2006; Reker and Wong 1988; Steger 2009; 2012).

With the introduction of the tripartite view, it is noteworthy that this approach tries to lean unto an already existing notion of meaning-frameworks, as this will make it more applicable to the broader literature and let itself be integrated. The understanding of meaning-frameworks is quite extensive, but as suggested by Heine, Proulx, and Vohs (2006), it can be understood in a direct correlation to meaning maintenance, where when the persons' understanding of themselves is threatened, different coping strategies are implanted in order to return to a world that *makes sense*. The implication of sense-making in meaning-frameworks, is also why the tripartite view is favoured here, as it takes into consideration exactly that, whilst at the same time taking into consideration the subjective judgements that are always imbued when discussing whether or not something is considered 'meaningful' to the first person lived experience, i.e. phenomenology.

Now to the matter at hand, when does a person experience her life as meaningful? And what is it that gives weight to more specific experience as having meaning? In the tripartite view, *comprehension* refers to the understanding and sense of coherence, which an individual has when looking at their own lives (George and Park 2016; Baumeister 1991; Reker and Wong 1988). Having comprehension of one's life is essential, as it first of all helps to make sense of the environment, and the relational place one has in their *Umwelt*, as well as a being able to properly handle and position experiences within a framework that does not otherwise fit into

a narrative. Inconsistencies in meaning frameworks and experiences can be violated by person, or world, altering experiences, ultimately generating distress. If unable to comprehend experiences that fits within a personal narrative, people will “experience an aversive state and engage in a wide variety of compensatory behaviours.” (George and Park 2016, p. 209), further evoking aversive arousal as well as undermining a sense of familiarity, leading to impairment of one’s capability of action, as events and experiences becomes incomprehensible.

Purpose is defined as that which an individual experience her life as having direction, and by being motivated by goals that are considered as valuable (George and Park 2016; Battista and Almond 1973; Klinger 1977; McKnight and Kashdan 2009). The sense of purpose is thus linked to having specified goals – George and Park suggests that goals can be categorized within a hierarchical scale, such as being a good parent is a high-level abstract goal, that can give cause to further low-level goals, e.g. making lunch for your child, driving them to school, spending quality time with them etc. High-level goals are what Carver and Scheier (1998) refers to as ‘*be goals*’, which means goals that are of the utmost importance to a specific individual, and what one aspires or desires to be as – giving not only a sense of purpose, but also a way in which a person understands herself, giving her a self-narrative of who she is and thereby also a sense of identity. Having *be goals* gives incentive to different routes of how to achieve these, and a person will be better equipped at adjusting her lower-level goals in order to do so. A lack of successfully achieving said valuable goals, will lead to negative consequences of a temporal aspect leading to emptiness and aversion, where “life ceases” (Carver and Scheier 1998, p. 346), and their whole identity will be threatened, as goals reflect one’s sense of identity.

In turn, *mattering* is an overarching feeling that individuals may have when considering their lives as having a certain degree of significance, importance, as well as value and worth in the world. The notion of mattering does not only pertain to specific intersubjective domains, but is rather an overall evaluation of worth and value in one’s life (George and Park 2016; Becker 1997; King et al. 2006). The feeling of mattering is by far the least researched by empirical standards, and is simultaneously quite challenging to narrow down, even so the feeling of mattering still plays an important role in having a meaningful existence – “most people do not go through life with the sense that their lives do not matter” (George and Park 2016, p. 213). Our lives are valuable to us, and many aspects seem to play into this overarching feeling – one might consider herself valuable towards her children and spouse, with a certain

aspect of significance and importance towards relationships, as well as in a more professional orientated dimension. And even though a creeping feeling of being worthless in light of history can intrude in one's life, the celebration of one's specific character often comes up during birthdays, weddings, and even funerals in the eulogy. We feel that we matter, we feel that we are important to others, we feel that we make a difference – it is through what we consider valuable that we evoke this feeling of mattering.

By enriching the enactive approach, one creates a notion of meaning directly correlating to values, that are individual subjective relative relations within our life-worlds: love towards another person isn't prefixed by an unconditional love as such, e.g. the love towards a parent's child. But is rather a value imbued relation *because* of said relationship; “Parce que c'était lui: parce que c'était moi” (Montaigne 1978, p. 266)¹⁸, that then becomes meaningful because of exactly the relationship between oneself and the other person. It just makes *sense*, there is no reason to explain, it just does. The sense-making that goes into such an evaluation is intuitive, where we add the reflective aspects later, when describing or distinguishing between different concepts or categories (de Haan 2020).

Sense-making and meaning permeates the way in which we interact with the world and shapes us, our actions, and reflectively our comprehension hereof. It is through our actions, that “our enactments of our stance-taking” (de Haan 2020, p. 128), and that we reveal an inner desire of what we consider purposeful and valuable.

This understanding of having meaning, living meaningful lives, and making sense of it, becomes increasingly interesting when considering the phenomenon of depression, as these three notions seems to falter when considering the depressive person's way of describing their experiences. This especially concerns the understanding of the suicide in depression, and how, as I will argue in chapter IV, the feelings of comprehension, purpose, and mattering return through the act, and the actions leading up to.

¹⁸ Eng: “Because it was him: because it was me.”

III. The Lived Experience of Depression

When discussing depression as a psychopathology within the realm of phenomenology, there has been established more nuanced ways of perceiving the disorder as such, which seeks to illuminate the way in which we are already in the world, and what happens when something goes amiss. These include embodiment, intercorporeality, intersubjectivity, affectivity and interaffectivity, and to better understand these terms it will be beneficial to consider them in a case study of severe depression, and how they are affected and affect tendencies and relations between ourselves, others, and the world. This third part of the thesis will therefore mainly focus on the works done in classic and contemporary phenomenological psychopathology and philosophy (Tellenbach 1980; Ehrenberg 2010; Fuchs 2014; 2019; 2013; 2005; 2001; Ratcliffe 2015; 2018; 2012; 2005) to try not only to explain the way in which we are in the world, but also to understand the fundamental structures of depression, as situated by beforementioned authors. It is worth mentioning that there exist different degrees of depression, ranging from mild, moderate, to severe, there also exist different varieties of depression including, for example: single episode depressive disorder or acute depression, recurrent depressive disorder or chronic, and dysthymic depression¹⁹. It is important to note, since the lived-experience of the patients pertaining to a specific form of depression varies (Ley et al. 2011), therefore, to narrow down the analysis, the rest of the chapter will be focusing on severe acute depression disorder unless otherwise specified.

III, 1. Personality Types

Beyond giving descriptions of the disorder, phenomenology has elaborated different specific descriptions to depression, which seeks to understand the personalities that are prone to developing this disorder in their lives. Two worth mentioning are the *Typus Melancholicus* as presented by Hubertus Tellenbach (1980), and the narcissistic personality type presented by Alain Ehrenberg (2010). Tellenbach did his research on phenomenological psychiatry, and introduces the *Typus Melancholicus* in *Melancholy: History of the Problem, Endogeneity, Typology Pathogenesis, Clinical considerations* (1980), which is considered one of the most important contributions for understanding depression itself, and the rising cases throughout the world (Micali 2019; Fuchs 2019). Tellenbach's project was to consider psychopathologies with a notion of phenomenology, trying to overcome the classic Cartesian mind-body relation with an introduction of endogeneity, and escape the two views of biological psychiatry and

¹⁹ ICD-11, <https://icd.who.int/browse11/l-m/en#/http%3a%2f%2fid.who.int%2ficd%2fentity%2f810797047>

psychoanalysis, where the former saw itself as a science whose scope lingered on the psychic's *somatogenesis*, and the latter concerning itself with abnormal reactions, developments and personalities through *psychogenesis* (Tellenbach 1980). Endogeneity saw to “[...] analyze the specific characteristics of psychopathological disturbances” (Micali 2019, p. 142), and encapsulate a understanding of what occurs in the alteration of the psychic at a given time, taking into consideration that which comes forth and emerges as whole in the entirety of the ‘autonomous system’ and correlating necessary processes (Tellenbach 1980). This means that the ‘autonomous system’ (the melancholic type), understood through the notion of endogeneity, is a different way of perceiving the individual where one seeks to understand *the unity* as now presented in its globality and “[...] what is all-encompassing in the inflection of the shape of existence. It is human being *in toto* which is transformed.” (Tellenbach 1980, p. 28).

The *Typus Melancholicus* is defined through a rigidity, conscientiousness, orderliness, overadaptation, and over-identification to social norms by being overly dependent and even symbiotic in relations (Micali 2019; Fuchs 2019), where “the melancholic’s conscience is in the first instance, a guardian of the established orders which permeate the world and the ties of the self.” (Tellenbach 1980, p. 122). Therefore, the melancholic type is prone to depression, as nothing can go out of order. They are careful and rigid in their routines and keep a strict order in their daily life – there is no allowance of change, as this would throw the individual out of their established orders they over-identify with, ranging from their environment to their social roles as parents, a good colleague, or as seeing themselves as a badminton player. This creates a very rigid world in which they operate, where their identity is fixated upon a dictated role as being such and such, in a light of a normative society. If this non-autonomous role is destabilized through falling “[...] short of their duties, if they experience unjustified rejections or the loss of significant others, then their world literally collapses.” (Fuchs 2019, p. 619), it potentially leads to a total transformation or *endokinesis* of the individual in question. In many cases for the *Typus Melancholicus* a severe depression is caused by an existential sense of guilt “through a qualitative ‘not good’, but also through a quantitative ‘not enough’” (Tellenbach 1980, p. 149).

Though the *Typus Melancholicus* has been found to be the most frequent variant of personalities in patients with major disorders (Fuchs 2019; Zerssen and Pössl 1990; Mundt. et al. 1997; Kronmüller et al. 2002; Stanghellini, Bertelli, and Raballo 2006), there seems to have been a shift within the last three decades. Where there has been a decrease in the *Typus*

Melancholicus in patients, the void left behind has then seen a steadier increase in patients with the narcissistic personality type (Fuchs 2019; Ronningstam 1996; Twenge and Campbell 2008; Twenge and Foster 2010). The depression for patients with the narcissistic personality is caused by an extreme individual expectation that is often impossible to reach, as touched upon by Alain Ehrenberg in *'The Weariness of the self: Diagnosing the History of Depression in the Contemporary Age'* (2010). Ehrenberg describes the narcissistic personality type not as the love of self, "rather, the experience of being captive to a self-image so idealized that it led to impotence and paralyzed the individual." (Ehrenberg 2010, p. 126), where the specific type needs constant affirmation in their environment and others, as to maintain a prevailing self-image, fixated by a more norm based cultural- and social setting. The individual is obsessed by maintaining a specific self-image, that is idealized to such an extent that it is unattainable, and the constant trying to reach said *peak* will potentially lead the narcissistic personality type to fail over and over again, never reaching what they believe to be the standard – thereby working harder leading to increased inefficiency, frustration, inner emptiness, and fatigue (Fuchs 2019). This is followed by a sense of weakness and inadequacy, as they perceive themselves to be inferior (Ehrenberg 2010). It is interesting to note that the narcissist will believe that she has created herself on her own, and will therefore consider herself to be responsible if she fails (Ehrenberg 2010). This is also where the melancholic and narcissistic personality type deviates in their depressions: the melancholic is haunted by guilt, the narcissist is troubled by an existential shame, since her logic is dominated by inadequacy, and where even the depression itself is experienced as a shameful flaw:

"The depressed individual feels shame, because, in [her] fundamental megalomania, [s]he cannot admit to [her] inadequacies; [s]he does not admit to feeling limited by reality, and in particular by the constraints imposed on [her] by [her] personal history and [her] affiliations." (Ehrenberg 2010, p. 129)

By *not* being limited by reality the individual with the narcissistic personality disorder severely handicaps herself by setting boundaries that eclipse her very own capabilities, although she does not impose the same degree of expectations on others. Even when the individual with narcissistic personality disorder amounts to significant accomplishments, she will neglect these as if they were nothing followed by a "sense of being less stimulated than one would prefer." (Ehrenberg 2010, p. 129). This could be because the individual has already moved on to new goals, before a given accomplishment have been completed, with even higher expectations than before, making just achieved goal fade in comparison.

It seems that through the rising focus on individuality that is noticeable through the different generations (Twenge and Campbell 2008), the individual with narcissistic personality type, now positioned in more and more globalized world, with growing competition that is no longer restricted to a local environment, is enabled by being told that they “can become anything that you set your mind to” furthering their traits of megalomania. Where options and choices in career and life goals seems unending, they attempt to do the impossible, and strive towards insurmountable goals of being the best in everything, where they are potentially betrayed by their finite skill and expertise (Micali 2010)²⁰ leading them to become depressed when faced with their finitude.

III, 2. Intercorporeality, Intersubjectivity, Embodiment & the Minimal-Self

In ‘*Depression, Intercorporeality, and Interaffectivity*’ (2013) Fuchs introduces known concepts in a context of depression and tries to explain the disorder as a restricted world, where one’s field of opportunities is narrowed down until the patient is isolated within herself and her own negative thoughts, unable to resonate with her environment in a *meaningful* way. Departing from the more western world view of what feelings are, where they have become distorted and to some degree inherited by a Cartesian dualism, Fuchs claims that depression is not an “‘inner’, psychological, or neurobiological disorder, [...] but a ‘detunement’ (*Verstimmung*)” (Fuchs 2013, p. 222) where the patient’s way of being in the world is altered. Fuchs therefore seeks to understand depression not as process within the patient, but rather as disturbance of intercorporeality and interaffectivity.

The importance of intercorporeality is that it paves the way for an understanding of interaffectivity, since they are closely connected to one another. Merleau-Ponty takes up the notion of corporeality in ‘*Phenomenology of Perception*’, which sought to maintain the point, made by Husserl, that the human consciousness is anchored in a corporeality. Husserl’s concept about consciousness has often been misinterpreted as a disembodied phenomenon, meaning a phenomenon that exists without a body. Rather, through Husserl’s analysis of double-sensing, Merleau-Ponty finds a sensing that reveals that I *am* body. When I sense my own hand sense, then I understand that I am my body. The lived body appears to itself in the experience, without needing a thematization – Merleau-Ponty repeats Husserl’s point: *Es Wird Leib, es empfindet*. Meaning that through sensing, the body as a physical thing, becomes the body that senses; it is body, it senses (Welton 2005; Husserl 1989, p. 152-3). First of all,

²⁰ Micali writes about the *typus melancholicus*, but I would argue that this is applicable to the narcissistic personality type as well.

the double-sensing gives phenomenology access to an unthematized experience of the lived body, unlike a thematized perception of the body, as for example in the sciences occupation with the objective body. Secondly, the double-sensing points at sensing as the primary access to the world. Merleau-Ponty also calls it for a *rehabilitation of sense-experience*, as it becomes possible to point at sensing as foundation for our primary experience of the world (Merleau-Ponty 1999). Merleau-Ponty deviates from Husserl, by saying that every experience is anchored in a corporeality: he denies the possibility that a human being can exist without a body, since the body is an ontological (necessary) life-link for man (Thøgersen 2004).

Other than intercorporeality and interaffectivity, Fuchs introduces the notion of *shared states* and *emotional space* for a further understanding that emotions are not just ‘inner’ experiences, but rather that we are situated in a world, that is not only inhabited by physical material objects, but also through affective qualities that ‘touches’ and affects us, that *matter* to us. We are able to understand the experienced space around us as emotions are often directed toward something with intention, as we for example experience and feel the coolness and bad mood when entering a room, and emotions can even be felt psychically when e.g. taking an exam, where the nervousness or anxiety position itself as a lump in your stomach or chest, thereby maintaining the notion that feelings are not just part of mental states, but are rather incorporated in our bodies. But this is not limited to other people, there is an atmospheric character that can emerge from situations and objects, where “Feeling befall us” (Fuchs 2013). Fuchs describes this as the emotional space, which is a form of meta-experience of our existence as both temporal and spatial, where the ‘I’ affect the world and vice versa. We are a resonant body, “a most sensitive sounding board in which interpersonal and other ‘vibrations’ constantly reverberate” (Fuchs 2013, p. 223). Meaning that we need to understand our body as a body with a “natural frequency” that in interaction with others’ frequencies creates fluctuations that will then *resonate* within us. Part of the resonance-body is *kinaesthesia*; we are motivated by feelings, we act accordingly to the behaviour of other people, and likewise change our facial expressions, when engaging in an interpersonal space, which indicate that we don’t just feel from the inside, creating the notion of intercorporeality since we are able to be affected by others through body language, which in turn is “the essential basis of empathy.” (Fuchs 2013).

Fuchs introduces Daniel Stern and his studies on ‘*The Interpersonal World of the Infant*’ (1985), as it becomes clear in the expressions of infants how much the intersubjective is affected by intercorporeality as a foundation for empathy, where one does not just understand

what others are feeling, but is indeed affected by others as beforementioned resonance board. Stern introduces three ways through which one affects and shares subjective experiences, 1) sharing the focus of attention, 2) sharing intentions, and 3) sharing affective states – it will be sufficient for the goal of this thesis to focus on the third way of subjectivity between subjects, which according to Stern is also the most important (Stern 1985). Stern seeks to show that by observing infants in certain situations, such as deliberately separating an infant and her mother: where the infant will most likely become upset or sad, one will be able to perceive the interaffective quality shared between people. In his observations he noted that the infants separated from their mother will stop crying when reunited, though they will remain solemn or unhappy based on the reaction of the mother. After the reunification, the infant will be shown a happy and a sad face, where they will prefer to stare at the sad face. But if you make the infant laugh or giggle, or if they had never been separated, they will choose to look at the happy face (Stern 1985). The experiment shows that one will seek affiliation in our environment and others based on an ‘inner’ mood, linking a more personalized notion of intercorporeality and intersubjectivity.

The notion of sharing affective states is that of interaffectivity or *joint affect*, where there are many aspects concerning interaffectivity, including moods. Moods function as an atmosphere, and just like a room can be either cold or warm, we all carry around our own personal sphere that will interact with other spheres of individuals. Fuchs mentions that we use descriptions of the weather to draw parallels to our own mood, which seeks to justify this feeling of a sphere around other individuals. Our moods then creates a consonance between body, consciousness, and environments, that ‘tune’ them just like an instrument – our moods functions as background feelings, that can be felt as a lightness in our body, or during a severe depression as heaviness, tiredness, burdened etc. (Fuchs 2013). It is worth mentioning that background feelings are not only related to an anonymous world but can also be shared with others in an interpersonal world, since we all have a need for an existential feeling of belonging. Interaffectivity is thus a collection of harmoniously cooperating aspects, that in union constitute a sphere around an individual:

“[I]t is the encompassing sphere in which our emotional life is embedded from birth on. This sphere has its centre in the lived body: through its affectability and resonance it mediates our participation in shared space of affective attunement.” (Fuchs 2013, p. 225)

The way in which we are in the world, and with this sense of belonging is attributed and rooted in our intercorporeality and interaffectivity, and it is the way that we are able to function and navigate our lifeworld's without being out of tune, and being receptive to others.

III, 2a. Failing Resonance in Depression

When an individual is disturbed and slowly glides into severe depression, the existential feelings will change, as the spheres, which surround us, will no longer interact as they previously did. One's empathetic capabilities will gradually degrade, and the resonance-body that constitute the interaction with others will disappear completely. This leads to 'false' attempts to fit in, which the patient will contribute to herself by appearing interested or empathic in certain situations, trying to mimic the other, as one *should*, because the depressed individual knows what the appropriate social norm-given response would be. The patient will realize that the attempts to fit in are ways of trying to hide their own expressions to either shelter themselves or spare others from their diminished capabilities of feeling or engaging. It is through this lack of bodily resonance, that they will have a reduced sense perception and recognition with the other (Fuchs 2013). The world in which one exists and belongs to is then disturbed during a depression with a growing psychomotor, as well as sensorimotor inhibition, and an overall general rigidity, that makes even the smallest tasks seem insurmountable. This phenomenon can also be described as a *corporealization* (Fuchs 2005; 2013) or *chrematization* (Doerr-Zegers et al. 2017) of the lived body, where the phenomenal space is no longer embodied. This not only affects the social life, but also eventually piles up one's duties creating a feeling of shame and/ or guilt that continuously grows, since one is unable to act upon one's aspirations and fulfil the responsibilities that the depressed patient expect for herself (Fuchs 2013; Tellenbach 1980). This furthers the feeling of alienation, where the individual is unable to be touched, affected by things, situations, and people, leading to a lack of feelings, understanding of spheres, and background feelings, as described by Solomon in '*The Noon Demon*':

“[A] loss of feeling, a numbness, [which] had infected all my human relations. I didn't care about love; about my work; about family; about friends...” (Solomon 2014, p. 59)

Depressive patients will complain of a *feeling of not feeling*, which should be allegedly contradictory painful (Fuchs 2013), although negative emotions, such as anxiety, hopelessness, feelings of guilt and shame, persist and increase. Fuchs derives three characteristics from these feelings; 1) They do not connect, but rather separate the subject from the world and from others, 2) Their bodily quality is characterized by constriction and rigidity, thus corresponding to the depressive state of corporealization, 3) They are embedded in the prevailing depressed mood rather than arising as independent feelings (Fuchs 2013). These characteristics help to understand how the lived experience of the depressed patient actually is. We are rooted in a need towards community, and when the interaffective part of us is diminished, social interactions will no longer be meaningful and feel empty, since one's lifeworld is no longer reflected in others. We are therefore bound to our respective society in how we perceive our world. When the patient loses her intercorporealization, she will be robbed of the needed cognitive abilities to put herself in another's perspective, and at the same time make her own reality relevant. Apart from a smouldering, isolating lifeworld, the interaffective sphere that usually helps to maintain an understanding world, becomes the only accessible realm. This forces the patient to make a correlation between herself and her depression, since this is the only option for recognition. Isolation therefore leads to feelings of rejection and shame where the patient perceives these as existential feelings, as the result of a lacking sphere – these delusions, Fuchs writes are “therefore rooted in the loss of the shared interaffective space and in the utter isolation of the self that results from it.” (Fuchs 2013, p. 233), pertaining to the idea put forward by Ratcliffe, that depression is an disorder defined by the alienation felt by the patient (Ratcliffe 2018).

Existential feelings are brought to attention by Ratcliffe in *Experiences of Depression* (2015): taking inspiration from Heidegger's *Dasein*, he deduces his own term “belonging to a shared world” (Ratcliffe 2015, p. 2). This implies that every human understanding works within a pre-reflexive feeling of belonging to the world, as already shown to be a fundamental part of our being-in-the-world. He argues that this belonging to a shared world is what is affected during a depressive state, where one's feeling of belonging is altered. The existential feelings constitute a space of opportunities within the individual subjectivity, and unfold the world for that individual. They can be understood as pre-intentional feelings, that are a way of finding oneself in the world. Existential feeling is described as either ‘the feeling of x ’²¹ or ‘the

²¹ ‘ X ’ should in this case be understood as a single word, such as ‘despair’, ‘hopelessness’, or ‘alienation’.

feeling of being *x*²² (Ratcliffe 2015), where, in mundane instances, it correlates to a cognitive self-evaluation, such as guilt – potentially accompanied by an assumed social evaluation concerning specific actions, that the individual deems unmoral. This evaluation can bring forth a feeling of guilt, where an intentional feeling of guilt, means to be guilty *of* something. When one's feeling of belonging is altered during depression, it implicitly implies that your whole identity is altered, which in turn leads to “altered bodily experience, loss of hope, feelings of guilt, a diminished sense of agency and self, altered experience of time, and isolation from other people.” (Ratcliffe 2015, p. 2). So, when one is depressed, the feeling of guilt can take the shape of something irrevocable and will be synonymous with *being* guilty. The guilt becomes part of the patient's essence, a character trait, or even a state of being, a guilt for existing itself (Ratcliffe 2015; Bortolan 2017). The possibility of positive self-evaluations is diminished or even excluded.

To summarize, existential feelings represent a way of understanding what is felt whilst containing a sense of reality and situatedness, thereby making it an affective experience and how one posits oneself in the world. If nothing goes amiss one is unlikely to notice existential feelings, but, when altered, the patient will feel as though ‘living in a different world’, thereby shifting the overall structure of world-experience, where everything looks the same, yet is completely different (Ratcliffe 2012; 2005; 2015). As a sort of overarching feeling towards the world, the depressed patients' existential feelings such as shame, guilt, and hopelessness, become a way of navigating the world. Wherever the depressive patient looks for possibilities in the surrounding lifeworld, she is imbued with these feelings as a sort of background feeling, constricting them even further, and alienating the subject's understanding of herself and the world, as it becomes progressively harder to feel reciprocated.

III, 2b. Crystallized Temporality in Depression

Together with the possibilities to act in the world, also the temporal dimension seems to register a disruption. Here the depressive patient no longer experiences time as her own, rather time flows over her as a steady stream washing over the patient. The patient will no longer have a sense of inner time, and there seems to be no options to grasp the future and look forward to new things, thereby slowing down experienced time. This inhibition of time disallows future possibilities, and the patient will dwell on past experiences with a negative

²² ‘*X*’ should in this case be understood such as ‘petrified’, ‘swallowed’, or, “in contrast, ‘at home in the world’” (Ratcliffe 2015)

perspective that situates guilt and shame as the overarching narrative towards prior experiences. Fuchs argues that, during depression, the lived time is considered as “monadic, without reference to intersubjective or social time” (Fuchs 2001, p. 3), that should not be considered as an individual inhibition, but rather as desynchronization of relations. This notion of desynchronization is closely resembled by the notion of resonance, where the intersubjective time becomes increasingly harder for the depressed patient to be in synch with, such as getting up on time, meeting deadlines, showing up for appointments, leading to increasingly feelings of guilt and shame. This eventually leads the patient to fall out of common time, leading her to live in another, sluggish time, that is not coherent with the intersubjective time, which is socially constituted (Fuchs 2001), giving the patient an experience of the future being blocked, and thus left situated in the past. This desynchronization with common time and stagnation of lived time further leads to general reduction of conative-affective dynamics of the body, as well as loss of drive, appetite, libido, interest and attention, since these are usually directed towards future positive prospects (Fuchs 2019).

The lived experience of depression is thus understood through a loss of intercorporeality or corporealization, interaffectivity, and excessive feelings of guilt and/or shame that have become existential and imbue the world and the patient with a feeling of *being* guilty as such – the world of the depressed have gone from pre-guilty to a guilty existence, and, concerning shame, the depressed is ashamed in the view of the other, even when she is alone (Henriksen and Skodlar, n.d.). As a resonance board the depressed patient is no longer affected by others leading to a desynchronization of common time where the future is unavailable, and possibilities no longer *present* themselves to the depressed patient. Almost as though living in another world, the depressed patient will complain about a feeling of loss of feeling, making them more and more isolated with feelings of alienation. This negative spiral is what keeps the patient in their depression, where they despair over themselves, or their inabilities towards others and own expectations. This is why “it is the relation of the “I” to itself that is threatened in depression, rather than the relation of the “I” to the world” (Tellenbach 1980, p. 166; Henriksen and Skodlar, n.d.) – if remembering the minimal-self, it seems rather apparent that it is the experiencer/ perceivers understanding of oneself that isn’t feasible to convey or understand in relation to a self-narrative. The fundamental structure of the pre-reflective is uprooted, threatening one’s sense-making and comprehension hereof, further distancing the depressive persons feeling of mattering, since they perceive themselves as being worthless

and without a clear distinct sense of value – especially seen in the two personality types, which so strictly adhere to an identity based in the world, where their purpose is to have these ‘*be goals*’, which does not necessarily carry over to actual goals of worth and value, but, as it will be shown, is rather about *what* is perceived as being worthwhile or valuable.

Then what are some of the problems faced in the current field of depression? The phenomenon of depression seems well researched and founded in adequate methods. But there seems to be issues or misconceptions in the literature concerning affordances as not *standing out*, lack of agency through a corporealization, as well as a desynchronization. Therefore, in the following chapter, through the use of a qualitative interview, I will try to nuance and bring new light to some of these misconceptions. My main aim is to show how *affordances are still very much there, that the person suffering from depression keeps their possibility of agency, as well as them living rich inner social lives – even in the severe and “darkest” part of depression*, all of the above mentioned still resides in the person. *And I will seek to show just how much the concepts of coherence, purpose, mattering, sense-making, and meaning are still there during the depressive stupor, especially in the depressive suicide.*

IV, Depression as Distorted Meaning and Values – Nuancing the Field

In this chapter I will argue that depression isn’t bereft of meaning, but rather that there has been a shift in meaning, and that depression is a disorder of distorted meaning and adoption of sociocultural, ‘public’ values, and meaning. This implies that meaning is still very present in depression, but that it is a particular meaning that isn’t experienced as meaningful to the specific individual. I will explore the possibility of adopting values by using Micali’s view (2010), as well as trying to show how, through the use of phenomenological interviews²³, depression isn’t only a corporealization, loss of feelings, intersubjectivity, interaffectivity, and common time, but there exists an overlooked variation to the disorder. I will argue that

²³ The hypothesis will be supplemented with phenomenological qualitative interviews of previously depressive people, which were conducted whilst working for Enactlab S/I, in order to give a more detailed account of depression. The reasoning behind choosing previously depressed people is based upon the fact that people with depression are, so to say, quite tough to actually have meetings with, as they will usually accept an appointment, but will on the set date, either 1) just not show up, or 2) cancel the appointment. The phenomenological qualitative interviews with people who had suffered from depression were done in correlation to a bigger project involving development of a curriculum to secondary high school, a theatre play, and an academic peer reviewed article currently in progress (Martiny and Frohn n.d.).

this aspect becomes apparently clearer during suicidal ideation, where the depressive individual is able to find a meaning, even if an unhealthy and distorted one, through suicidal thoughts, research, notes, and fantasising about one's own funeral. Furthermore, through the qualitative interviews, it is possible to see how:

Action and agency are still present when faced depression, as well as rich inner social lives,

The corporealization of the lived body can be considered as a coping mechanism due to overload,

The depressive individual is hyperaware of norms, values, being 'good';

Performative tasks negatively imbue their world and affordances.

I will therefore argue that the field of affordances isn't toned down, grey, or receding as traditionally conceptualized (de Haan et al. 2013; Bruineberg and Rietveld 2014): rather, in depression, it bears similarities to the field of affordances in OCD. This analysis and discussion aren't meant to contest the validity of the work done in the contemporary field, rather it is meant to show the experience of depression in a new light and suggest changes that could prove insights for the understanding of this disorder.

IV, 1. Method

The participants of the interviews were recruited through the organisation 'En af Os'²⁴, where an interview-invitation was emailed to all their subscribers. The respondents to the invitation were chosen based upon diversity in gender for the sake of variety, age ranging between 18-60, and having experienced depression within the last three years. In total 12 people were interviewed with the participation of 7 women and 5 men.

The interviews lasted between 1-1½ hours, and were all recorded, transcribed, and have been analysed, coded, categorised, and reheard several times. The interviews were conducted and based upon EASE (Parnas et al. 2005), EAWE (Sass et al. 2017), EAFI (Rasmussen, Stephensen, and Parnas 2018) as well as other studies (Hammersley and Atkinson 2007; Giorgi 2009; Zahavi 2015; Høffding and Martiny 2016). The main aims were to let a first-person experience emerge as to try and understand the phenomenon of depression in itself.²⁵ The focus of the interviews was to let the participants own detailed descriptions of their lived

²⁴ Eng. 'One of Us' – a Danish association that seeks to destigmatize mental disorders and the people suffering from it by writing newsletters, essays, establishing events, campaigns, conferences etc.

²⁵ See chapter I, 2. A Phenomenological Approach for more detailed account of the phenomenological interview.

experiences be the centre of attention, and let these come forth by using ‘open’ questions. These sought to let the persons reflect and use a language that isn’t heavily influenced by common and professional terminology, by bringing attention to their specific situations and staying with these e.g. waking up in the morning.

All the participants names have been anonymized for the sake of privacy, and their statements translated from Danish to English.

IV, 2. Adoption of values

The participants of the qualitative interviews all addressed problems of facing a meaningless existence, where *nothing* would touch them. A man describes his encounter with depression in these terms: “I couldn’t find meaning in anything, and even though I had a lot of friends that I could call, I felt all alone, and couldn’t find a reason for anything at all.” (Male, 33). But the idea of people suffering from depression as having no meaning nor feeling seems debatable, since the results of the qualitative interviews shows just how much they feel, and how much meaning there is in others, even when they are in their ‘darkest’ moments. One woman describes as such, how even in the midst of her depression, she is still able to get out of the door, and pick up her grandchildren:

“There is nothing that is meaningless, when one [man] pick up a one-year-old from nursery. They run to greet you, and then you have to pick up groceries from Netto [Danish grocery chain]” (Woman, 57)²⁶

To understand what happens when people experience meaninglessness in a world that was otherwise perceived as meaningful, and how it is possible for the participants to experience positive feelings and meaning, even during their depressive stupor, it will be favourable to consider the discrepancy between personal values and societal, public values. In *The Capitalistic Cult of Performance* Stefano Micali (2010) asks the question of the possibility of capitalism taking on a role of religion. More importantly, concerning the scope of this analysis, he raises the view of ‘the cult of performance in the post-disciplinary societies’, in which he applies Tellenbach’s mentioned notion of remanence in order to understand the link between the sense of being left behind in an always progression world, being in debt for not living up to expectations, and depression (Micali 2010). Micali asks us to consider that the

²⁶ Translator’s note: the Danish word ‘*man*’ has a strong normative aspect to it when used in spoken language – ‘man’ could be translated to ‘you’, but by doing so the overarching implied normative behaviour is lost, therefore I have chosen to translate it to ‘one’, as it better encapsulates what is meant. Furthermore, it does not seem like the participants are aware of the normative implications in their used language, which could be inquiry for further research.

different personality types, i.e., the attitudinal constellations, aren't inherently given to us by nature, but rather is something that is learned or *produced* through our environment and *Umwelt*, and if so, what does that mean for us as people of the post-disciplinary societies? If remembering how our sense-making and stance-taking revolves around a 'body-world dance', and that the individual, with a minimal-self, is formed and shaped by the environment that surrounds it, Micali's proposition does not seem farfetched. And even if the attitudinal constellations are that of nature, then there surely must exist an environment that will enhance the characteristics of the *Typus Melancholicus* and that of the narcissistic personality type, just like there would exist a place that would diminish their traits. The world in which we live certainly seems to accommodate the aforementioned traits of these two personality types (Twenge and Foster 2010; Ehrenberg 2010; Hidaka 2012) with the constant pressure of improving, progressing, evaluated performance, and applying worth to our actions and accomplishments on both a local level of self-identification and identity, as well as on a global societal level of fitting into a certain frame.

This extreme adherence to performative society and an overidentification with its norms and values is quite noticeable in the interviews, and one man describes in numerous ways how one 'should be':

"They [an employer] had been so kind to take me in when I was going through a really tough time. And then one feels obligated. I have a strong moral character... if there is someone helping me, then I feel compelled to help them... There are some specific ways to be... So, I feel that society does a lot for me, so then one has to do everything one can, to give something back." (Man, 32)

These normative, precise, rigid ways to be, and expectations to live up to in social and societal spheres, invoke strong feelings of obligation towards others and society – as though they are debt and owe something of value. These ways of how one ought to be and act quickly become performative tasks for the participants, and the social obligations are present even in situations that are commonly considered positive. Almost every interaction becomes a stage where the person has to perform, which is, undoubtedly, exhausting, and takes a huge toll on them, as they never have a break from expectations and to constantly be the best version of themselves, in the light of what they *believe* to be 'good'. One woman describes this overarching performative notion:

“It’s a performance to exist... It is the core of the disease that I should pull myself together. This is connected to the fact that I am what I perform. So, if I don’t accomplish anything, then I am nothing. And then I should pull myself together, because if I want a value, then I need to do something. And why should I not be able to do anything when other people do it every day and get up for work – what is it about me that makes me unable to pull myself together?” (Woman, 33)

Her quote showcases the interconnection that Micali argues for through remanence, of being left behind, feeling indebted, and depression. Since it has even become a task to exist, she is in turn also constantly evaluating herself through either a good or not good enough, as having a certain worth. In her eyes, what is considered worthwhile or valuable is linked and always compared to an Other, and her whole identity is bound up on said value, and her whole system has been transformed *in toto*. A few examples of how almost every single participant’s identity is strictly interconnected with performance and value:

“If I am not good²⁷, then I am not worth loving.” (Woman, 32)

“I needed to study medicine, because then I was good – if one did that.” (Woman, 39)

“I need to do something extraordinary, if I am to receive praise.” (Man, 24)

If we consider these statements, it appears clearly that this unreasonably rigid understanding of being a ‘good’ person allows for only commendable things to appear, which instils high, even unachievable, self-expectations. This confirms Fuchs’ point according to which when they fall short of their duties, their world literally collapses (Fuchs 2019):

“I had bond up my value as a person on my work, and when I had to realize, that I actually couldn’t do it, then it all snapped completely.” (Woman, 39)

One of the participants, when asked about how she experiences the Other during depression, answers:

“Then I am even more focused on what others might think. As soon as there is another person, it doesn’t matter what they see, it just isn’t good enough. It is an inadequacy and I have them with me under the duvet.” (Woman, 44)

²⁷ Translator’s note: I will consistently translate the Danish word ‘dygtig’ with ‘good’, but ‘dygtig’ means so much more than just good and consists of many implicit connotations. One could call it an umbrella term, that encapsulates positive descriptions such as: skilled, capable, clever, sharp, able etc.

The participants become hyperaware of the Other, and continuously compare themselves hereto with increased feelings of inadequacy. The Other does not necessarily take on a specific physical form, and continues to exist even when alone and isolated, and it closely resembles Heidegger's notion of 'das Man'. 'Das Man' is an understanding of a public 'no one' and everyone, that dictates a way of being as *one* should be, through a "Botmäßigkeit der Anderen [...] [wo] Diese Anderen sind dabei nicht *bestimmte* Andere." (Heidegger 1993, pp. 126).²⁸ This notion is very applicable to the statements made by the participants, and shows how das Man affects their way of being in the world – they constantly make remarks as to how 'one' is supposed to behave and act, and failing to live up to the normative ways of being furthers their feeling of mentioned inadequacy, and they will absolutely take this home with them and continue to ruminate about it, as "das Man ist überall dabei." (Heidegger 1993, pp. 127).²⁹ - which is the danger as well. 'Das Man' isn't anyone in particular, meaning that their individual ruleset and understanding of what is *good* isn't necessarily the common adherence to public, normative rules, but something quite individual and imagined. The person with depression won't expect others to navigate through life with their strict and rigid rules; it, paradoxically, only applies to themselves, although they continuously talk of how *one ought to act*: "I think that they have a right to be sick, but I need to get my act together." (Woman, 33)

In light of 'das Man' it becomes apparently clear how the participants show an adoption of values, and what is considered meaningful – or a sort of taught overidentification with performance: work titles with intrinsically bound worth. The depressive individual perceives that to be meaningful, as to not be left behind, and *if* left behind, they will develop a feeling of existential guilt, debt, or shame for not living up to the expectations in a world that requires all too much, where one has to be proficient in sports or arts, take courses to learn a language, play an instrument, get a house, get married, have children, excel in a professional landscape, keep up with friends, host dinner parties, get good grades, go on vacations, be updated on global and local politics and economy, see the newest art exhibition, and so on. Which then "generates in the individual the sense of being intrinsically inadequate." (Micali 2010, p. 386). Sociocultural or 'public' values and meanings have *seeped* through the depressive person and replaced one's first-person meaning and in turn become one's 'new' meaning framework, both reflexively and reflectively, that imbues the system *in toto* with

²⁸ Own translation, Eng: Submission to others – [where] these others are not specific others.

²⁹ Own translation, Eng: das Man is everywhere.

notions of performativity and normativity. To summarize, what a person considers valuable and meaningful is in a depressive stupor replaced with public, normative values, that are not inherently meaningful to the individual herself, although she believes it to be. Thus, the depressed person keeps on pursuing goals and achievements that *should* give her positive feelings, it instead makes her wonder why she isn't feeling accomplished. Or it can also happen that she adheres to unachievable goals, since she does not realize her own finite aptitude, leading her to fail over and over again, and leading to feelings of existential shame and the belief of not being good enough. The whole existence becomes permeated with normativity and performance because of this adoption, which then affects agency, sociality, and their narrativity.

IV, 3. A New Understanding of the Lived Experience in Depression

The last subchapter slightly alluded to the misconception of a lack of agency in depression and corporealization of the lived body, since the act of picking up one's grandchildren from nursery clearly shows the possibility of action, intercorporeality, interaffectivity as present even during a depression episode. Accordingly, it seems that the understanding of depression, as presented by the contemporary field, isn't fully nuanced.³⁰ Though new perspectives arise from the interviews, they likewise clearly show a classical understanding of depression, take for example the affirmation of the corporealization and the loss of feelings as presented by two participants:

“My experience was that I was laying there, a petrified thing, that was physically paralyzed by something that I didn't know what was, and I thought it was my fault, and thought that I was wrong and stupid.” (Woman, 57)

“There was a complete lack of feeling, and nothing mattered anymore. And it wasn't even that nothing mattered, because then you would have considered it.” (Man, 32)

Rather, I seek to show how there is variation and graduation in the lived experience of depression. Even the quote by the woman, that exemplifies the corporealization of the lived body as petrified, shows that, although unable to act and gain control of her body, she still has high and intense cognitive awareness of her inabilities:

³⁰ Again, it is important to address that I am not denying the work done by Fuchs and Ratcliffe, the failing resonance, corporealization, and desynchronization in depression, nor what was presented in chapter III.

“The head is not petrified because it is alert about everything that happens around oneself. It is the volume of everything, that it is just too much... [I: What is it that takes up so much thought?] People. Because I know they’re right outside the door.”
(Woman, 57)

The Other, again, plays a dominant role in their shortcomings, and the pressuring thoughts about what other people might think, expect, and demand incapacitates them, as social norms towers over them, making them unable to act upon basic needs such as eating, getting dressed, waking up on time etc. When asked about their morning, their thoughts, and feelings especially social performative tasks comes to the foreground.

“I can’t even be bothered to brush my teeth, everything is a huge task – and when you have children, then you *have* to get going. I haven’t been able to just lie down, and let myself erode, even though I want to. Everything is about the thoughts; ‘how can I escape this?’ After all, I can’t commit suicide, because I have children. So, it is all plans about how I can best escape this.” (Woman, 33, own italics)

The social performative tasks that one *must* or *should* do hinders the participants, and their own understanding of what is expected of them is all that occupies their mind, making them highly aware of everything they aren’t capable of doing. But when further inquiries were made, it became apparent that many acts of agency were still present through examples relating to responsibility towards close relations, getting up and making breakfast for the children, getting them to school etc., although these were still seen as overly normative demands. It demonstrates how the loss of agency and corporealization of the lived body ties itself to overwhelming, demanding social performative tasks that one *should* or *must* do.

If we look at the broad consensus of depressive people as having a lowered, grey, rather flat field of affordances, where nothing stands out as being attractive, and the phenomenal space is no longer embodied (de Haan et al. 2013; Bruineberg and Rietveld 2014; Fuchs 2005; 2013), it does not seem to be entirely true. Because, if considering how the individual see’s everything as a performance, then the act of getting a glass of water isn’t just a local, immediate affordance of a basic need, but rather a global imbued affordance full of overarching normative demands, that requires too much of the person.

“Even something as basic as getting a glass of water. It simply is a task so big, that one would rather sit and stare into nothingness.” (Woman, 44)

It is a global affordance that reflects directly back to their whole being, and confirms how ‘bad’ of a person they are – since they aren’t ‘even’ able to do such a simple task. A permanent causal explanation can for the depressive, for example, be to attribute a character trait, instead of assigning it a certain behaviour, or lack thereof, as just a bad mood or day. According to Bortolan (2017), this sort of narration has its seed in the depressive existential hopelessness, which means a hopelessness of such a grave calibre, that encompasses all and everything such a potential hope could set its roots in. Thereby, corporealization becomes a sort of defence mechanism or escape from overly demanding existence imbued with responsibility, as expressed by a woman, when describing what she experiences as ‘the black’:

“It is thoughtlessness - Which there is actually something pleasant about, instead of having ugly, negative thoughts, which are actually worse than going into zombie-mode.” (Woman, 32)

The field of affordances of the depressive individual isn’t toned down or ‘grey’, as portrayed in the sketch (de Haan et al. 2013)³¹, rather they are extremely explicit and closer resembles the field of affordances of a person with OCD³². The person with depression sees her very being, her whole identity, as bound up in something exterior to prove and show her worth, making her life-worlds extremely vulnerable and fragile to either drastic change or realizing her finitude through inadequacy. The affordances represent ways in which to either prove or disprove their identities – so in order to protect the ‘I’ in relation to itself, it simply *shuts down*

the system. This also seems to explain why it is symptomatic for many people suffering from depression to extensively sleep or isolate themselves. A young man who constantly battled

³¹ The borrowed sketch represents the different field of affordances – although the describing a field of affordances as “normal” can be stigmatizing, and I would rather refer to such a field as people with no diagnosis – especially if considering Merleau-Ponty and how it doesn’t make sense to ascribe the “normal” everything that the “abnormal” or sick is missing (Merleau-Ponty 1994, p. 53-4)

³² Obsessive Compulsive Disorder – In OCD the affordances are linked to thoughts of anxiety, and are relieved through compulsive actions (de Haan et al. 2013).

the need to be extremely social, but also an intrusive urge to be alone, created this flux of conflict between personality and narrative, of being *good*, but feeling terrible:

“I had a greater self-image than my self-evaluation could meet or recognize in the social interactions. That is probably also why I preferred to not have those interactions, because then I didn’t have to make those choices, and then I wouldn’t have to do the *right thing*. Then it was better to not be confronted with the fact, that I couldn’t figure out how to be a good person.” (Man, 24, own italics)

He would rather not venture out into the world, than to have his self-ideals challenged, because when alone, there would be no expectations of how to behave, which was first experienced as a sense of freedom, but left him to become increasingly lonelier, since the social interaction was also considered indispensable for him. Not only is it the self that can be proven inadequate, but they also believe themselves to be a burden to others – they see themselves as disrupting the lives of others and creating problems where they aren’t able to be of equal value to their peers, as they fall short of performing in the same manner as the Other, and their existence becomes pre-guilty. This fixation, or even hyperawareness, of the social domain is quite symptomatic – one woman describes how, a month before a wedding, she started to consider different excuses for not showing up, and the thought of the wedding occupied most of her thoughts, whilst counting down the days leading up to the day, what worries her, is the thought of:

“people having a lot of thoughts of how bad a person I am. And everything that I do is wrong, and I have known beforehand that they have judged me. I haven’t opened myself up, and [have] been quite dismissive, since it is better than being rejected... overthinking tiny things, analysing, and turning things over – even long after.” (Woman, 33)

This seems to suggest not a utter isolation, but a rich social inner life, that exists within the depressive person, and unlike Solomon’s descriptions, where “I didn’t care about love; about my work; about family; about friends...” (Solomon 2014, p. 59), the participants actually care obsessively about all of these relations, even if only in the form of a comparison to an Other, to negatively confirm their pre-guiltiness, or shamefulness. The social dimension clearly plays an important role in depression and ties itself directly to the notion of what is experienced as meaningful, and it shows how the supposedly utter isolation of the self does

not seem to fully encompass this aspect of the condition, as the social interaction can vary depending on the context:

“That is why [social interactions] are so tough. Because putting yourself in the social situation can both be the cause of you breaking, but it can also be the cause for you learning to see the [whole] situation better. Which is the hardest – to give others a chance.” (Woman, 44)

The constellation then shows how meaning emerges from relationships in the *Lebenswelt*, where it implies that there is a difference between performative obligations full of expectations and the immediate freedom from responsibility, normative rules, and the danger of the self-narrative being challenged. This safe space varies depending on the context, but especially close relations play an important role, “if you sit with your phone, then there are sometimes some children or girlfriends, that has sent a little message, or I receive a video of my grandchildren – then I become attached to the world again.” (Woman, 57).

To recapture the different points presented through these phenomenological qualitative interviews, the enactive approach and its categorizations is quite inspirational for making clear delimitations: the existential, biological, and social.

The existential domain, that includes the notions of the loss of feelings, and lack or loss of meaning, also includes the existentialised sense-making and stance-taking – the common understanding of such – is usually represented by existential feelings that pre-intentionally gives a feeling of belonging. In depression this layer seems to be disrupted. But the accounts of the participants show how there is still the possibility of feelings, and not only the negative emotions, but also positive ones, such as meaning, “happiness[,] and joy” when spending time with her grandchildren – furthermore there are examples of humour, even if gallows humour:

“I have been able to laugh about it [the suicide] since then. [I: Even when you were down?] Actually yes, I thought about the hunting rifle that had to have a specific angle, otherwise you will just shoot your jaw off. And that was almost Storm P. like [Danish cartoonist], and I thought that it was [so] incredibly comical that it was absurd.” (Woman, 44).

The existential feelings and the understanding of felt emotions varies greatly, and the participants are also able to understand the sense of reality and situatedness, and it then isn't

just a loss of interaffectivity nor intercorporeality – this still occurs, but they are also able to understand social spheres and emotional space. They simply are able to be moved and touched by body language and nearness.

In direct correlation to their variation in emotions, they all, without exception, immediately describe their days as though they aren't able to do anything, and everything is *dark* and *hopeless*, but when inquiries were made to take the interviewer through one of their days, they all describe variations. One describes a "day-variation", which I would like to call an *afternoon-animation*. As their days start, it is with troublesome concerns and feelings of emptiness, that won't let them leave the bed, but as the day progresses, it becomes more and more manageable, "I become more and more active, then I can think different thoughts and feelings." (Woman, 57). This also shows how their field of affordances isn't grey and as not standing out, but they are actually able to act upon the solicitations – it is an instability in their lives, full of hyper-sensitivity, that is overly performative and challenges their rigid and strict self-narrative.

This leads to the biological domain and to the belief that their world isn't experienced as a horizon of possibilities: A horizon with no actions, nor initiation, which again seems to be problematic. In fact, their statements clearly show that psychomotor and sensorimotor inhibition, or corporealization, isn't the main feature of depression. On the contrary, the interviewed subjects seem to be able to do many things, such as getting up and packing lunch for their children, and they actively embody the phenomenal space, even if greatly burdened by social, normative, performative tasks. Even if the actions are small, and can seem rather insignificant, such as cooking dinner in a 'private social sphere', they still persist.³³

This in turn touches upon the notion of social disconnection, and that they are actually hyperaware of this dimension. In fact, if socially numb, how is it possible to experience such immense guilt and shame? They might, at times, physically isolate themselves, but they continue to live an inner social life, and the desynchronization of common time as monadic without references to the intersubjective or social time is a bit unnuanced, as it can be experienced as a *good*, and they still adhere to responsibilities that they deem of great importance; Nonetheless, it seems that the intersubjective encounter must be on their own premises. This brief summarization of some of the nuancing points will now be made even more explicit in the case of the suicide.

³³ This will especially be shown in the following case of depressive suicide.

IV, 4. The Depressive Suicide as the Last Meaningful Act

There exists a great variety in the causes leading to the suicide, and it is important to underline that here we are talking about the suicide following a depressive episode, or simply put: the depressive suicide. According to Benson, Gibson, and Brand (2013) the suicide is a reorientation towards an existence that has become so intolerable that the only possibility of escaping is suicide. De Haan also takes up the notion of the possibility of suicide as an escape from “not being able to cope with this present life anymore.” (de Haan 2020, p. 139), which seems correct to some extent. The suicide *is* a flight from a life full of pain, misery, and nothingness, as seen in this account:

“[I: How did you experience the suicide?] Liberating. Very liberating... It has maybe been my way of thinking of freedom. If you weren't here, then you wouldn't need to consider anything at all.” (Man, 49)

But at the same time, the depressive suicide offers a possibility of regaining a horizon of possibilities, even if very finite. I believe the common conceptions of the depressive suicide to be misunderstood, or lacking in depth, as this form of suicide stems from a new inner delusional meaning in life, that the person suffering from depression finds attractive, as it seems to rekindle a sense of *comprehension*, *mattering*, *purpose*, and *temporality*, that has otherwise been ‘*missing*’. The lack, or diminished agency in depression, as presented by the depressive people themselves through the contemporary field, becomes problematic, especially because there is a greater adherence to the thought that the suicidal self is a “self for whom agency is disrupted or depleted” (Benson, Gibson, and Brand 2013, p. 77); This seems refutable by revisiting the interviews:

“[I: Have you written suicide notes?] Yes, those I have a lot of! I came to an [online] forum, where I discovered, that you could get these things down on paper. And how productive I was, gosh! [I: Even when it was worst?] Yes, that I could do.” (Woman, 44)

She feels that she is unable to get a glass of water, but the act and prospect of writing poems comes easily to her. How is it that the action of writing poems, spending time on an online forum, is possible, whilst suffering from depression during the ‘*darkest*’ time and a corporealization of the body? The example by this woman isn't a singular incidence, the other participants confirm it too, and they all show the same possibility for agency:

“I tried, at one point, to get a hold of cyanide pills online, but I couldn’t get them. That was in my darkest moment, where I tried to do so.” (Woman, 32)

Affordances then aren’t receding: they’re standing out in a particular *light*. Achieving this in ‘darkest moments’ reveals a possibility for change, unlike some of the other signs of agency in depression. The interviews show how, even in the midst of a depressive stupor, they’re able to research the suicide, and how to perform it either painlessly, or in such a way that will not expose close relations to the aftermath. They spend an incredibly amount of time writing both suicide notes and letters, to let others know that it isn’t their fault. All these actions revolving around the suicide aren’t experienced with psycho- and sensorimotor inhibition. There is no rigidity, quite the opposite:

“[I: How do you experience writing something?] It is like getting fresh air, because you have a mouthpiece, where you can be anonymous.” (Woman, 44)

The writing of letters and notes is a way for the person with depression to be social and interact with others on their own premises, where they don’t risk the possibility of being rejected – the isolation experienced in depression is ‘reverted’ with the suicidal letters, where they’re able to connect with others non-physically, and their felt alienation is diminished, as they inhabit a meaningful world once again. They *feel* reconnected to the world, as these small moments of experienced freedom are rid of their otherwise overwhelming existential feelings of guilt and shame. They are able to synchronize, resonate, and feel the possibility of being reciprocated in their current situation, although it is with an imagined other. The social aspect is of such utter importance to the suicidal depressed individuals that they will spend hours on end to make sure others around them will be left of “okay”. It seems the notion of loss of interaffectivity and loss of the intersubjective realm falter, as they are extremely empathetic towards the position occupied by others.

“I have fantasized a lot about my own funeral, where there is a lot of love connected to. And then also the planning [of the suicide], and how to be considerate – where you could [do] it, where it could be tidy, so people aren’t traumatized. Who should receive farewell letters, what to write in them, I had to consider organ donation, so that there wouldn’t be too much of a burden.” (Woman. 32)

Considering that the suicide is final, the fixation with the social aspect of their lives is quite interesting, as they still go out of their way to contact or write family members to make sure they aren’t blaming themselves for what happens – It goes against the notion that the

depressive person does not care, like described by Solomon earlier, and seemingly negates the general idea of there being no agency nor horizon of possibilities, because the participants were able to take control of their body, spent time and energy researching the suicide, and be free from normative, exhausting demands. It, then, raises the question of *why* they suddenly are able to regain their agency, unfold their social lives, and experience the freedom associated with no social obligations and norms and the guilt and shame that originates here. It is the regaining of subjective personal meaning and the tripartite MIL.³⁴

With the suicide, the future seems to become available by letting the individual synchronize with common time with references to intersubjective or social time, even if very finalistic. A horizon of possibilities presents itself to the suicidal depressed person, offering reprieve from an otherwise stagnated, corporealized, desynchronized existence. *Comprehension* of one's situation returns when suicidal, as 'things seem clear', giving the depressed person a sense of life as becoming more coherent, less fragmented, less desynchronized. They understand their situation, and the choice of the suicide creates a frame that isn't overly complex, rather it is quite simple, and offers an escape from their situation, allowing coherence on how to act, reconstituting sense-making and stance-taking in which they're able to position experiences within a framework that didn't fit with their narrative, furtherly permitting a synchronization imbued with *purpose*. There is a sense of direction and end towards their striving – the suicidal person gains a clear aim, a goal to pursue and obtain, which is considered valuable to them, a '*be goal*' (ending the suffering), but also reconnecting to loved ones for whom they *matter* or *matters* to them. Taking back their existence as having relevance through rich social inner life, and fantasize about the reception of their suicide, the letters, funeral – a romantic idealization of the suicide, as we all wish to experience a certain degree of significance and importance towards relationships.³⁵ Reconnecting to their closest in their own solitude, often leading to spouts of energy as they have quite a clear outlook of their immediate future, as it makes more sense, they're being directed and motivated, and thereby finds *meaning in life* by letting go of all that has been weighing them down and getting rid of their guilt and or shame. Therefore, it seems to show how there is a certain value and meaning that comes forth in a depression, even if an unhealthy and skewered one. It is the

³⁴ If remembering the chapter concerned with meaning, the tripartite view of MIL was offered as a possible outline for analysing meaning which included the three notions of *comprehension*, *purpose*, and *matter*.

³⁵ Take for example Goethe's '*Der Leiden des jungen Werther*' (Goethe 1774), where the young Werther, due to heartache, commits suicide, as he sees no possible future without his loved one, which transgressed into a wave of young people committing suicide in Germany with Goethe's book in their breast pockets.

resurgence of everything which encapsulates the tripartite view that the depressed person has lacked for the duration of their disorder, now giving them a feeling of meaning, and thereby making the depressive suicide the last meaningful act.³⁶ Their sense-making, as de Haan argues for, has been disturbed, and the way in which they perceive and understand their world and environment does not inherently make sense to them. Prior to their depression their world was imbued with a meaning that they're now lacking, making them unable to make sense and stance-take on their own position – therefore, in order for the world to make sense, they implement different coping strategies. And since their whole identity is often bound up on something exterior to themselves, and the 'I' is threatened, they discover their identity anew through the suicide, as it positions them in a certain light with a feeling of mattering and a relation to the world once again, re-establishing the body-world dance.

The depressive suicide then isn't what is more commonly argued for: the notion that "For the suicidal self [...] they are now someone with '*no hope, direction or future*' and the sense of an enduring self is diminished or even lost." (Benson, Gibson, and Brand 2013, p. 69) – or as Fuchs puts it: depressive suicides are the "realization of the overall standstill of time and loss of intersubjective contemporality." (Fuchs 2019, p. 625), which leads to the paradoxicality of both being a restoration of the future, as well as a means to annihilate it. Though the suicide might stem from a hopeless situation that in itself seems to have no direction nor future, i.e., loss of possibilities and temporality, as well as the intersubjective aspect, it is also through the suicide that the suicidal depressive person is able to find structure in their lives, that makes it seem comprehensible again, as well as connect on an intersubjective level, that they deem important – Viktor Frankl writes:

"The spiritual human freedom, you cannot deprive a human of it before it dies, giving it the possibility of making life meaningful, just as long as it exists. For it is not only an active life that has meaning, as it only gives humans the possibility to realize values in productive activity [...] Even in the most difficult situations and right to the last of minute of life, there opens a wealth of opportunities for making life meaningful." (Frankl 1959, pp. 71-2, own translation)

Frankl, through his surviving of the concentration camps, saw that even in the most soul crushing experiences, people are always able to find meaning in their situations. The same is

³⁶ This in turn perhaps explains why it is possible to observe people in close relation to people that commit suicide often reports an increase in their (i.e. the person committing suicide) sociability, outgoingness, energy, and general perceived happiness days before the act or attempt

true of the person with depression, as they up to the last minute of their suffering existence. They try to make sense of their *Lebenswelt* and find meaning by connecting to others through the suicide, silently or explicitly. As the suicide is an act imposed on oneself, they all still seem unaware, or rather naively unaware, or even delusional about the finality of committing suicide, as they idealize the suicide as a mechanism that give them back what they have been seeking for so long, which then leads to unwanted suicide attempts with potential dire consequences. The attempts, that does not end up with death, usually ends with the individual seeking help afterwards, as well as the time spent leading up to the suicide shows what is fundamentally important to the person with depression: the intersubjective relation with another, that isn't burdened with normative, sociocultural demands or expectations of being in a certain way. It could be, just as how the whole system is transformed with existentialised sense-making and stance-taking, the system again is transformed during depression, which isn't farfetched, considering how the reflexive and reflective understandings of personal engagement with the world is always co-constituted by an Other and the environment, thereby picking up a mantle of new existential stance, that has changed one's perception and stance of oneself, as well as experiences, and the consequences that follow from here.

The phenomenon of depression then isn't just "Hopeless, meaningless, and sad... sometimes thoughtless, sometimes not, *it varies*." (Woman, 32, own italics). Fuchs describes depression as a disturbance, or *Verstimmung*, of intercorporeality and interaffectivity, Ratcliffe as an illness defined by the alienation felt by the patient, and de Haan as a disorder of sense-making. These understandings are correct, but still seem to lack the *variation* experienced in the different dimensions, as described by the participants. Through my analysis, it becomes visible how depression is also an adoption of sociocultural, normative worth and values, which the two personality types are exceptionally susceptible to perceive as *meaningful*, thereby adopting them and making *Zeitgeist be goals* their own. Nonetheless, they aren't meaningful to the particular individual, further misaligning and alienating the feelings felt towards herself, as well as towards others. De Haan's point concerning biased sense-making, that through a lasting pattern amounts to a disorder, allows for a view of adopted values to come forth, as the way in which the depressive individual makes sense of the world; A world that has become overly normative and demanding, leading to self-imposed unreasonable and unreachable expectations that over time leads to a depressive episode, where the depressive individual has a tough time understanding their position towards themselves and their world. But the adherence to the theory that the world of the depressive as being 'grey', 'dark',

‘empty’ without any soliciting affordances, no common time, nor agency, just isn’t correct, as the “afternoon-animation” shows: it isn’t a complete loss, rather *‘it varies’*.

What then does this variation in depression matter?: Since it is dangerous for the people suffering from depression to integrate such an ‘grey’ narrative, as it seems that all the participants have this picture of them not being able to do anything – and when asked about this self-perception, showing them that they are *actually* able to do multiple things, they show a cognitive dissonance between their self-narrative and actuality. They have bought into an understanding of what depression is, i.e. the operationalistic understanding of depression, as per the two diagnosis manuals. The risk and danger of a misunderstanding of depression, not only leads to misdiagnosis, over- and under-diagnosis, but also affect the people either suffering from or suspecting the disorder, as they will research it online, get their knowledge through the media, pop culture, and thus use the same words to describe what they’re experiencing. This leads the person suffering from depression, who is already quite rigid, systematic, and perfectionistic, to understand themselves through such notions that in turn affects their narrative, stance-taking, and sense-making. This does not only conform to depression but also other disorders in psychopathology, as a fixation on the common language and metaphors used by people with depression as well as their practitioners shows only certain aspects of a particular disorder, but not necessarily a more holistic picture, potentially leading to the adoption of a narrative that isn’t entirely aligned with actuality. Therefore, a nuancing of language, diving deeper into their descriptions, and not only taking their experiences at face value, will undoubtedly show a lived experience full of variations, which might point towards underlying issues and causation, that will be beneficial for both treatment as well as research methods applied in the fields of psychiatry, psychology, and phenomenology.

Conclusion

Operationalism and the ICD-11 & DSM-V has in this paper been viewed as insufficient, in regards towards depression, the patients' experiences, as the disorder involves so much more than what the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale implies. Although, as we try to include a first-person lived experience, we mustn't neglect that biological and somatic changes are still observable during a depressive episode – and must therefore undoubtedly be involved for an adequate understanding hereof.

In this paper I have presented different theories from the contemporary field of phenomenology in hopes of clarifying why exactly a first-person perspective is overly important within the field of psychiatry and psychology, if we want to achieve better understanding of mental disorders. Since, as Fuchs (2013) states, if we are to continue calling depression an affective disorder, then we have to cast aside the idea of it residing in the psyche or brain, and rather view it as a detunement to an interpersonal world, where the whole system is transformed. The blooming of phenomenological psychopathology has brought with it new explanations and methods, but psychiatry needs an integrative model to include many of the different dimensions and aspects that cause mental disorders, which is why the inclusion of the enactive approach, in forms of an enactive psychiatry was proposed as favourable (de Haan 2020), as it seeks to resolve the relation between subjective and objective approaches, and pave the way for a more integrated approach, that takes into account the enormously complex notion of individual and world.

Furthermore, with the use of the notions of sense-making, MIL, and the presented landscape of depression understood through the scope of phenomenology, a broader understanding of the phenomenon has been instigated. Through the use of phenomenological qualitative interviews, conducted with Enactlab S/I, it has shown that the phenomenon still requires attention, as it was possible to observe a variation in the lived experience of people with depression. This observation shows how in depression there is still possibility for action and agency, understanding of social spheres, emotional space, emotions such as humour, happiness, and joy – meaning that it isn't just a *loss* of intercorporeality, interaffectivity, and intersubjectivity. The corporealization of the lived body with no embodiment of a phenomenal space still occurs, but this state of being is rather a coping, or survival strategy, in a world that requires too much from the individual, and is therefore only one aspect of what depression entails.

I have argued that meaning persists during depression, but it is a meaning that isn't a personal meaningfulness, rather it is an adopted, overly demanding, normative, sociocultural meaning, that the depressive individual, especially the two presented personality types, i.e. *Typus Melancholicus* and the narcissistic personality type, has adopted and incorporated into their own existence, leading them to live lives that *doesn't make sense* to them with overarching feelings of guilt and shame, as they aren't able to be 'good' and 'valuable'. Their narrative of who they are has been affected, and thereby their sense-making and stance-taking, making them isolate themselves, because venturing into the world first of all challenges their fragile self-perception in regard to an Other, confirming the idea that it is the 'I' in relation to itself, that is being threatened, but also their world has become overly normative, resulting in permanent causal explanations. Their field of affordances are therefore not receding, but standing out, as they are no longer local, but rather global, making even minor tasks insurmountable. This adoption of values and norms leads them to live lives that are experienced as meaningless, reducing their perceived possibilities, and as a last desperate attempt to regain a sense of comprehension, purpose, mattering, and temporality, they consider suicidal ideation and the depressive suicide, as it allows them to engage in a body-world dance once again, and gives them a, distorted, feeling of meaningfulness. This investigation not only confirms the need for a model that incorporates a subjective and objective approach, but also calls for further inquiry for the phenomenological description of lived experience in depression, as, to my knowledge, this variation and afternoon-animation has yet to be even further explored.

Abstract

The understanding of *meaning* within psychopathologies seems inevitable, since psychiatric disorders pertain to the way of how one interacts, understands, feels, or makes sense of the world and oneself. But within the DSM-V and ICD-11 the patient is often overlooked, and only conforms to the disease in a reductionist view, thereby missing the real core of the pathology, which is the patient herself (Bizzari 2019). A phenomenologically inspired enactive perspective offers the idea that psychiatric disorders are disorders of sense-making, affecting the way in which people relate to themselves, their world, and other people; as such, an enactive approach puts the patient in the foreground with their lived-experience (de Haan 2017). Accordingly, we can conceive psychopathologies not only as a deviance from ‘*normal*’ behaviour, but also as something so ingrained in how we act upon and engage with the world, through a constant sense-making that “discloses a meaningful, value-imbued world” (de Haan 2017) in an individual first-person intuitive process.

Therefore, this thesis will revolve around contemporary phenomenological research including, just to name a few: Thomas Fuchs, Matthew Ratcliffe, Sanneke De Haan, and with the works of these aims at establishing a foundation that will lead to an analysis of how distorted sense-making shows that *meaning* is an integral part of psychopathology. Therefore, I will show how a skewed *meaningfulness* in the world greatly impacts the lived experience, and I will analyse the specific meaning of subjective experience such as embodiment, intercorporeality, intersubjectivity, and interaffectivity, notably by using the tool of phenomenological qualitative interview.

In particular, I will make use of a specific case study: depression, a psychopathology that involves a huge disruption in each of these structures. I will argue that it seems to be not a *loss* of meaning, but rather it seems to be an indirect pre-reflective distortion that in turn *changes* or *shifts* the feeling of *meaning*, and that the lived experience in depression is full of *variation*. Then, I will focus on suicidal thoughts in depression, and I will show how this alteration of the self can only find *meaning* in suicide and suicidal thoughts, by tying up the misconceptions of a *lack* of *meaning*, and shifting it unto a first-person perspective of generating meaning.

The final aim is a clearer understanding of both *meaning* and sense-making in depression, that might offer a more nuanced perspective of how they *work* when the self is somehow disrupted. Thus, I will show that a phenomenological enactive approach within psychopathology will further the understanding of mental disorders.

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